

scientia

Undergraduate Journal of Scientific Research
University of Notre Dame

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of Biodiversity**
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Perspective in Research

by Dean Gezelter

Dear College of Science undergraduates,

There's an interesting anecdote about Alexander Fleming's discovery of penicillin. When Fleming saw a petri dish that showed the presence of a new antibacterial agent, he did not shout "Eureka!" [I have found it!]. Instead,

"... Fleming while explaining the staphylococcal work to Pryce, to demonstrate a point, picked up one of the top layer of the discarded plates when he noticed the lysis of the staphylococci (his cry of Eureka was 'That's funny!') and then and there made a subculture of the mould."

It is often said that the most important words in science are "That's funny!"² or "that's odd..." or "what the heck?"

Discoveries in science do not jump out and announce themselves. They rarely happen if we sit under an apple tree waiting for something to land on our heads. Discoveries often happen when we carefully design an experiment to disprove a hypothesis, and the experiment works as intended. *Sometimes*, however, scientific discovery happens nearly by accident, when a researcher is deeply engaged in an experiment, simulation, or derivation, and the world simply refuses to cooperate. Many people might interpret this as a failed experiment, some buggy code, or a missed sign in a derivation. These interpretations will often be correct. All scientists can make mistakes, so we need to be vigilant and investigate all causes of results that don't make sense.

In a few rare cases (and maybe just a few times in a career), *after* we eliminate the experimental errors, *after* we fix the buggy code, and *after* we step through that derivation carefully with a colleague, that perplexing result is *still* staring us in the face. And that's the most important moment in scientific discovery - the moment when 'that's funny' becomes 'why is that happening?' These are the moments when scientific discovery invites us in.

I have been lucky enough to experience this feeling a few times in my career. In one particularly memorable example, Christopher Fennell, a graduate student in my lab who is now on the faculty at Oklahoma State University, was working to parameterize a new computational model for water. He was running a set of liquid simulations at different temperatures to look at how rapidly the water molecules were diffusing using the new model. One simulation out of the hundreds he had run that week showed that the molecules weren't diffusing much at all. It looked like they were stuck in a very odd arrangement. We spent the next few days looking carefully at our simulation code: Had something gone wrong? After eliminating the likely sources of error, the student and I sat together and teased apart the structure of water molecules that had become stuck in place. We noticed that they formed a *new* crystal structure of ice, and it was one that had never been seen before! Then the hard work began to understand *why* the new water model was trying to crystallize into something ice-like, but not exactly ice.

The history of science is replete with accidental discoveries that occasionally outshine intentional discoveries. The lesson is that it is important to recognize the feeling of "that's funny." It means that something in your mental model of the universe is not adding up and needs further investigation.

I also want to highlight that scientific discovery can happen to *anyone* who prepares themselves well and remains open to these "funny" moments. It can be hard to see yourself in the ranks of the great scientists if you don't feel

like you belong. How many discoveries have been overlooked simply because the people who made those discoveries didn't look like what their contemporaries thought scientists should look like? Most of us are now aware of the contributions to the DNA structure that were made by Rosalind Franklin, but how many other women in science were overlooked before we started recognizing intellectual giants like Jennifer Doudna (who worked on CRISPR) and Carolyn Bertozzi (who pioneered biological uses of 'click' chemistry)? In the world of physics, an important experiment in 1956 showed that parity is not conserved under weak nuclear interactions. This experiment was carried out by the physicist Chien-Shiung Wu, an expert on beta decay, who was overlooked by the Nobel committee that awarded the 1957 prize to the theorists who originated the idea of parity non-conservation. Chien-Shiung Wu became one of the most important experimental physicists in history, and was instrumental in the creation of the Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP). In 1964, at a symposium at MIT, she asked her audience "whether the tiny atoms and nuclei, or the mathematical symbols, or the DNA molecules have any preference for either masculine or feminine treatment." Science is here for *everyone*!

As you read this issue of *Scientia*, take a moment to think about the moments of discovery and all of the hard work that led to each of these articles. I also want to encourage you to amplify and encourage your fellow students no matter where they come from or what their background is. May *all* of us be lucky enough to experience those rare moments of scientific discovery!

In Notre Dame,
J. Daniel Gezelter, Ph.D.
Professor of Chemistry and Biochemistry
Senior Associate Dean for Education and Undergraduate Programs

¹*Introduction to the History of Mycology* by G. C. Ainsworth, p. 219, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, England, 1976.

²This sentiment is often attributed to Isaac Asimov, but no source of the quote has been found.

Letter from the Editors

Since 2009, *Scientia* has been a force for supporting scientific research in the Notre Dame community. Our student-run organization provides a space for Notre Dame undergraduate students to publish their scientific research, spotlights students and faculty that are conducting interesting research at Notre Dame, and helps students practice the skills of scientific writing and editing. Through *Scientia*, students and faculty at Notre Dame are able to both share their research and knowledge and also learn about the research that is happening all around them.

During our time as Editors-in-Chief, we have been grateful to support the mission and lead the next chapter of *Scientia*. We

were able to grow and expand *Scientia's* presence and reach within the College of Science, demonstrated by a record number of applications to the Editorial Board and attendees at our Talk Science events. We expanded our Editorial Board with the addition of a talented student photography team, which has greatly contributed to our growth in marketing and recruitment. We are proud to have hosted six successful Talk Science events throughout the 2023-2024 academic year, which spotlighted a wide variety of research from students and faculty studying biology, environmental science, chemistry, biochemistry, neuroscience, mathematics, physics and astronomy.

This year, we are honored to celebrate the 15th year of *Scientia* with the publication of Volume 15. Through featuring a diverse range of student publications, this volume explores the many contributions that members of the Notre Dame community have made in the field of science. From developing models for prostate cancer, to exploring the advancements of artificial intelligence (AI) in scientific laboratories, the journal takes an inside look into the remarkable work done here at Notre Dame. We hope this edition inspires your curiosity and fuels your enthusiasm for the fascinating research happening on our campus. It is through inclusion, collaboration, and intellectual curiosity that we can progress and make a long-lasting impact on the scientific community together.

The creation of this journal would not have been possible without the dedication of our hard-working team. A special thank you goes out to our incredible Editorial Board for their passion and commitment to promoting scientific research at Notre Dame. We are grateful to Brooke Friedman, our Chief-of-Staff, for her wonderful planning, organization, outreach skills, and contribution to our Talk Science events. Sincere appreciation goes to our advisor, Dr. Xuemin Lu, and the College of Science Marketing Communications team, including Lotta Barnes and Deanna Ferrell, for their invaluable mentorship and support. We are excited to pass on the roles of Editors-in-Chief to Andrew Dinh and Josh Moeller and Chief-of-Staff to Noelle Dorvault and are confident in their leadership for the 2024-2025 academic year. We look forward to seeing what *Scientia* will accomplish in the future. Go Irish!

In Notre Dame,
Kayla Nguyen and Stephanie Swegle
Editors-in-Chief

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College of Science Faculty Spotlights

This section features some of the new faculty members that the University of Notre Dame recently welcomed to the College of Science.

Dana Horgen, PhD

Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Associate Teaching Professor

Dr. Horgen earned her bachelor's degree (B.A.) in Chemistry from St. Olaf College located in Northfield, Minnesota. During her time as an undergraduate, she worked on a summer research project at the University of Minnesota focused on small heterocyclic molecules for drug activation and completed a 5-month study abroad program across four different universities. She then completed her doctorate (Ph.D.) at Baylor University in Waco, Texas. There, her research focused on small molecule synthesis and she worked on two specific projects; phosphorus ligands for asymmetric hydroformylation and azulene based diastereomer analysis. She also enjoyed serving as president for the Chemistry Graduate Student Association, graduate assistant to the Dean of the graduate school and completing a yearlong program called TeaCHE Teaching Certificate in Higher Ed. Prior to arriving at Notre Dame, she worked at Rhodes College where she spent a lot of time on curricular development between the introductory lab sequence and lecture classes. Dr. Horgen became interested in her field of study because as an undergrad, she enjoyed doing organic synthesis. She felt like she was accomplishing something by using her hands and getting to problem solve during reactions and the analysis afterwards. One of her favorite things about her job is creating experiences for students to have that "ah-ha" moment where they realize that they have accomplished something by completing a lab experience. She believes that organic chemistry doesn't have to be limited to white powders and clear liquids, so she likes introducing the colorful compounds to students as well. For fun, Dr. Horgen enjoys running and erging. She has completed over 20 marathons and is working towards completing the Abbott World Majors!

Saurja DasGupta, PhD

Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Assistant Professor

Dr. DasGupta received his B.Sc. in Chemistry from the University of Calcutta, and his M.Sc. from the Indian Institute of Technology Bombay. He obtained his Ph.D. in Chemistry at the University of Chicago, where he used X-ray crystallography to study a special class of RNA molecules called ribozymes that possess enzymatic properties. His research uncovered structural and chemical principles that allow certain RNA molecules to function as enzymes. During his time as a graduate student, he was a member of the University's Spiritual Life Council and Science and Faith discussion groups on and off campus. Enthralled by the versatility of RNA, he moved to Harvard to explore the various roles RNA likely played in the emergence of life on the earth. As a postdoc, he explored the roles RNA-based primordial enzymes may have played at the origin of life by artificially evolving these enzymes in the lab and testing their functions inside synthetic models of primordial cells. Since 2019, he has been serving as a contributing editor at Club SciWri, a science communication outlet of STEMpeers, the world's largest network of STEM professionals. As a new Assistant Professor at Notre Dame, his group will intensify his efforts at cracking the mystery of Life's Origins and resurrecting extinct biology with the ultimate goal of creating a living cell from scratch. His group is also invested in developing new technologies to illuminate poorly understood RNAs in extant biology. Dr. DasGupta has always been interested in Origins questions. He loves the fact that Origins of Life has a philosophical flavor to it, which makes for thoughtful conversations with people outside science. Dr. DasGupta says that his time in research has been a matter of designing a roadmap, following it, and never giving up. He is excited to be at Notre Dame because he believes this campus will provide a lot of opportunities for him to interface with scholars in philosophy and religion.

College of Science Faculty Spotlights

Tyler Coverdale, PhD

Department of Biological Sciences, Assistant Professor

Dr. Coverdale earned his Bachelor of Science in Ecology and Evolutionary Biology from Brown University in 2010, and his Ph.D. in Ecology and Evolutionary Biology from Princeton University in 2018. He then went on to be a Presidential Postdoctoral Fellow at Cornell University between 2018 and 2021 and a Postdoctoral Fellow at Harvard University between 2021 and 2023. As an undergraduate and postbac researcher, Dr. Coverdale studied the causes and consequences of salt marsh die-off in England's salt marshes. His research as a Ph.D. student then focused on understanding the effects of large mammalian herbivore declines on African savanna plant communities. His work focused on the defense responses of plants to declining herbivores, shifts

in plant community composition under simulated herbivore extinction, and particularly the effects of elephants on understory plant diversity and abundance. His postdoctoral work expanded on these same topics to include more chemical ecology and remote sensing approaches. At Notre Dame, his lab works on similar questions in African savannas and North American prairies. His lab members are broadly interested in understanding whether and how plant communities will be resilient to human impacts, including climate change, fire suppression, herbivore extinction, and habitat destruction. The lab uses field experiments, mathematical models, chemical and molecular ecology techniques, and remote sensing to address these questions. Dr. Coverdale began his undergraduate studies intending to major in history, but took an introductory ecology course on a whim and never looked back. He was fascinated by the idea that ecology could be a career - that one could spend their life working in the field, designing experiments and interacting with nature, all in the service of solving some of the world's pressing ecological problems. He loves that his work is fueled by his own curiosity and informed by observations of the natural world. He notes that there is something uniquely rewarding about noticing a pattern in the ecosystems where he works, fitting it into the broader body of ecological theory, and then designing new experimental or observational approaches to understand what caused it.

Kelsey Gasior, PhD

Department of Applied and Computational Mathematics and Statistics, Assistant Professor

Dr. Kelsey Gasior received her B.S. in Applied Mathematics from the University of Michigan and her Ph.D. in Biomathematics from North Carolina State University. She was a Postdoctoral Researcher at the University of North Carolina in the Department of Biology and Department of Mathematics and then a Postdoctoral Scholar at Florida State University. She also lived in Ottawa, ON, for 2 years while she was an Assistant Professor at the University of Ottawa before coming to Notre Dame. Her research focuses on understanding multiscale cellular patterns through

mathematics. She studies changes in cellular behavior that allows for carcinoma metastasis during a process called the epithelial mesenchymal transition (EMT). She also studies a second area of research, which analyzes the process by which proteins and RNAs rapidly demix from to form liquid-like condensates in the cytosol and the nucleus. One recent collaboration resulted in her mathematical model correctly predicting protein organization in ALS-associated condensates and her collaboration results were published in Science. When Dr. Gasior was younger, she didn't show much interest in mathematics or science beyond what was required. When she reached high school, she had a fantastic teacher who helped show her that mathematics was all about problem solving. Then, at UofM, she started exploring a few applied mathematics courses and a friend of hers recommended the Introduction to Mathematical Biology course. This was the second time in her life it felt like things shifted into place. With biomathematics, she found a lot of joy exploring real world phenomena through the lens of mathematics. For Dr. Gasior, mathematics is like putting on a pair of glasses - the world makes more sense when she is looking at it through that lens. She loves exploring real world phenomena with mathematics and discovering the patterns that govern cellular behavior. She notes that each piece of an equation encompasses a different piece of the overarching biological process and it all fits together to give us a better idea of what is going on. If Dr. Gasior could offer one piece of advice to any student, it would be to go to office hours as much as possible. She encourages students to ask their professors about their research - she says that they love to talk about it! Dr. Gasior wants students to hear that you never know how you're going to be inspired or what area of science you'll become interested in!

College of Science Faculty Spotlights

Nirmal Ghimire, PhD

Department of Physics and Astronomy, Associate Professor

Dr. Nirmal Ghimire is an associate professor in the department of physics and astronomy. He uses material synthesis as a tool to design and discover new and emergent phenomena in quantum materials and study their magnetic and magnetotransport properties. He received his B.S. and M.S. in Physics from Tribhuvan University of Nepal in 2003 and 2005, respectively, and Ph.D. from University of Tennessee at Knoxville (UTK) in 2013, working both at UTK and nearby Oak Ridge National Laboratory. He then moved to Los Alamos National Laboratory to pursue postdoctoral research. In 2015, Dr. Ghimire joined Argonne National Laboratory as a Director's postdoctoral fellow. In 2018 he moved to George Mason University as an Assistant

Professor in the department of physics and astronomy. He joined Notre Dame in 2023. Dr. Ghimire's awards and recognitions include NSF CAREER Award (2021), Dean's Award for Early Career Excellence at George Mason University (2020), Director's Postdoctoral Fellowship from Argonne National Laboratory (2015), Seaborg Fellowship at Los Alamos National Laboratory (2015), Chancellor's Citation for Extraordinary Professional Promise (2015) and Outstanding Graduate Teaching Assistant (2013) University of Tennessee. Dr. Ghimire has co-authored more than 55 peer-reviewed journal articles that are cited more than 10,000 times. During high school, Dr. Ghimire was fascinated by physics in general. What impressed him the most at that time was to learn how eclectic current is generated by changing the magnetic flux lines and how magnetic fields can be generated by using the electric current. His current expertise is in growing materials, especially in single crystalline form and studying their electronic and magnetic properties. He chose this particular field of study during his Ph.D. after realizing how impactful new materials discovery can be in shaping our future technology. Dr. Ghimire notes that material discovery is very rewarding. In fact, entire human civilization has been marked by materials. For example, different ages in human history have been named after materials: stone age, bronze age, iron age, and the present silicon age. Silicon technology was discovered in the 1950s, and we all now know how it has shaped our lives in terms of technology, reaching the limit in terms of designing faster, smaller and more energy efficient devices. Dr. Ghimire's enthusiasm lies in addressing this grand open challenge by designing new compounds in hope of discovering a material that can take human civilization to the next level in a way the materials mentioned above did.

Petr Stepanov, PhD

Department of Physics and Astronomy, Assistant Professor

Dr. Stepanov, an assistant professor in the Department of Physics, started his academic journey at Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology (State University) for his B.Sc. degree, where he found his passion for physics, especially through hands-on lab classes. He got more into experimental science, focusing his bachelor's and master's theses on improving the thermoelectric properties of nanostructured materials. Finishing his graduate studies at UC Riverside and Ohio State University, he explored various 2D materials, digging deep into the topological properties of electronic systems and spin-transport in graphene-based antiferromagnetic insulators during his doctoral research. Using state-of-the-art electronic

transport measurements, he uncovered the phenomenon of magnon transport via graphene's quantum Hall ferromagnets. Starting his postdoctoral appointment at the Institute of Photonic Sciences (Barcelona, Spain), he investigated the quantum transport properties of strongly correlated electrons in twisted bilayer graphene. His research not only revealed how electronic interactions could be manipulated but also shed light on the complex effects of screening on phase diagrams. In the latter part of his postdoctoral tenure, he delved into the study of strongly correlated phenomena in moiré materials, utilizing advanced cryogenic near-field optical imaging techniques. At Notre Dame, Dr. Stepanov remains dedicated to studying light-matter interactions at extreme confinement in two-dimensional quantum materials. His unwavering belief in unraveling the interplay between light and matter to unveil their inherent properties fuels his tireless commitment to advancing knowledge and breaking new ground in experimental research. His fascination with science has always driven his career path. He finds great satisfaction in exploring quantum phenomena within condensed matter systems. He believes it is truly remarkable to witness the significant impact it has already had on science and technology. He says that quantum matter lies at the core of future electronic advancements, making it crucial to understand its properties for the continual advancement of technology and scientific exploration.

Michael McConnell, PhD

Department of Biological Science, Associate Professor of the Practice

Dr. McConnell grew up in South Bend, Indiana, and obtained his B.S. degree in Biochemistry from the University of Notre Dame. He went on to earn M.D. and Ph.D. (Microbiology and Immunology) degrees from the University of Michigan in Ann Arbor. Before joining the Department of Biological Sciences, Dr. McConnell was head of the Hospital-acquired infections Unit at the National Centre for Microbiology in Madrid, Spain. His research focuses on characterizing antibiotic resistance mechanisms and developing novel vaccines for the prevention of infections caused by antibiotic resistant bacteria. He is a founder of the biotechnology company Vaxdyn, which develops therapeutics and vaccines for bacterial

infections. Dr. McConnell began working in the vaccine field during his doctoral studies at the University of Michigan, and has continued to work in this field over the following 20 years. He enjoys working in vaccine development because it brings together many different aspects from different fields such as microbiology, immunology, public policy and global health. He believes that vaccines hold great potential in combating some of our most pressing global health problems, such as antibiotic resistance. He has a special interest in the development and implementation of vaccines in low resource settings.

Lee Haines, PhD

Department of Biological Sciences, Associate Research Professor

Dr. Haines received her B.A. in Biology from Trinity Western University. She completed her Master's in Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, with a specialization in Parasitology at the University of Victoria. She then earned her Ph.D. in Tropical Medicine, focusing on Vector-Borne Diseases, from the University of Liverpool. Dr. Haines describes her scientific journey to be similar to the art of fly fishing. She knew she wanted to immerse herself in the river of knowledge, and find an outlet for her insatiable curiosity on how other species live, communicate, survive and thrive, but she didn't have enough experience or knowledge to feel like she could ask the right questions. To master fly fishing, one should learn how to read the

water, think like a fish, know how to mimic aquatic insect species, balance on slippery river rocks, and cultivate patience and resilience. Her scientific journey was filled with different skills she needed to learn once she became smitten by medical microbiology as an undergrad. This allowed her to explore the fascinating world of parasitology, which inevitably led her to the world of entomology. Her primary research focus explores how insects respond to different stressors, how insect-infecting parasites thrive within the insect host and the dynamic interplay between the insect's microbiota, the insect itself, and the parasitic inhabitants. With more than 20 years of experience with parasite culture and insect husbandry, she managed the largest operational tsetse fly breeding colony in the UK. Her expertise further extends to rearing colonies of several mosquito species, triatomines, and sand flies. She is a passionate science ambassador and is involved in events that showcase the wonders of insects and microbes. This has included activities like science festivals, youth workshops, science blogs, and radio shows. Dr. Haines is also a tenacious advocate for women in science, and strongly believes in supporting and uplifting young scientists at all levels in STEM. Furthermore, as a mental health and well-being champion, she has supported many colleagues and students throughout her career and continues to place highest priority on sustaining an educational journey that interweaves knowledge and creativity. What truly captivates her about science is its profound connection to the past, present, and future, and that it can transcend geographical, personal, and political boundaries. She loves building a collaborative landscape encompassing these zones of overlap because it is undeniably where creativity thrives.

College of Science Faculty Spotlights

Quynh Lan Nguyen, PhD

Department of Physics and Astronomy, Associate Research Professor

Dr. Nguyen earned her B.A. in Physics at Vinh University, where she also got a full scholarship to attend the high school for gifted students in mathematics. After graduating college, she became a teaching assistant at Vinh University and took care of her children. Years later, she returned to graduate school and got a Ph.D. in theoretical particle physics, focusing on the Higgs boson and dark matter in the beyond-standard model in particle physics. She received her Ph.D. in Theoretical Physics from the Institute of Physics, Vietnam Academy of Science, followed by her JINA postdoc at Notre Dame, a Scholar at the Department of Theoretical Physics at CERN, the Yukawa Institute for Theoretical Physics at Kyoto University, and The

Kalvi Institute of Theoretical Physics at the University of California Santa Barbara. Following her postdoc, she worked on the beyond-standard models in cosmology for cosmic evolution, inflation, cosmic microwave background and foreground. Dr. Nguyen is a member of the LIGO-Virgo-KAGRA (LVK) collaboration and the PI of the Notre Dame KAGRA research group, which includes undergraduate students. Her research involves studying beyond standard models' new physics and its constraints with astrophysics, cosmology, and gravitational waves observations. In 2014, when she was a chair of the general physics division at Hanoi National University of Education, Prof. Takaaki Kajita, director of the Institute for Cosmic Ray Research at The University of Tokyo, gave a talk on the progress of the building of KAGRA, the first underground gravitational wave detector located in Japan. He said he wanted to do something new, and it inspired Dr. Nguyen to start working on the gravitational wave. She would love to use gravitational waves as a probe to study dark matter and investigate dark matter imprint in the gravitational wave signal from compact binary coalescence and other gravitational wave sources to explore the universe and creation. Dr. Nguyen's dad, an astrophysics professor, inspired her to believe that physics is beautiful. She uses the quote "standing on the shoulders of giants" to describe what she loves about science. Conversation with God daily is the most important factor driving Dr. Nguyen and encourages her to continue researching astrophysics and cosmology. She likes playing piano and running with her dog in her spare time.

A New Era for the Museum of Biodiversity

Carmelina Komyatte, '25

The Notre Dame Museum of Biodiversity in Jordan Hall of Science has recently acquired an expansive collection of taxidermied animals donated by Greensboro Science Center (Greensboro, NC) and Kaleideum Museum (Winston-Salem, NC). This collection includes the mounted giraffe in the Jordan Galleria, a lion, a tiger, two leopards, a cheetah, bush pig, hyena, wild dog, four antelope-type animals, a dik-dik, mountain goat, rhino head, elk head, water buffalo head, black bear, and nearly 100 birds. This exciting new addition to the museum, facilitated by Dr. Joanna Larson, Assistant Curator of the biodiversity museum and Assistant Professor of the Practice in Biological Sciences, ushers in a new era of growth and publicity for the Museum of Biodiversity.

The Notre Dame Museum of Biodiversity houses over 750,000 specimens including plants, mammals, insects, birds, reptiles, fish, amphibians, and more. The

museum is operated by the curatorial team, Barb and Ron Hellenthal and Joanna Larson, and a cast of undergraduate students working for pay or doing undergraduate research. This small staff works to facilitate research for Notre Dame and external researchers, help instructors use museum materials in graduate and undergraduate courses, run public open houses, and maintain and catalog existing specimens.

That's right, the Museum of Biodiversity is still cataloging its collection. This might be surprising to students who assume that the museum has been continuously maintained since its establishment, but alas, our museum has had a tumultuous history that the current team is still catching up from.

The very first Museum of Biodiversity was established in 1844, just two years after the founding of the University, by Father Sorin who acquired a large collection of specimens from a land trade. This collection, which was housed in the Main Building, was mostly destroyed in

the Main Building fire in 1879. Rev. John Zahm was then assigned to rebuild the collection in the old Science Hall (now LaFortune Student Center) where it stayed until the 1950s.

The collection moved to Hagger Hall in 1952 and then to Galvin in 1971. Since each move came with less and less space for the expansive collection, lots of specimens and documents were lost. From 1971 to 2006 the museum lay dormant, the collection spread across campus closets and faculty offices. Professors kept the specimens they wanted, but most were abandoned in closets; no one was in charge and nothing was cataloged!

Thanks to the design, advocacy, and motivation of Professors Ronald and Barbara Hellenthal, the Museum of Biodiversity was reestablished in Jordan Hall of Science upon the building's completion in 2006. The Hellenthals and a group of undergraduate students worked tirelessly to find, move, and catalog more than 300,000 specimens that were previously stored in random closets and offices around campus. This was a huge task, and today the museum staff are still working to identify and catalog specimens found in that move.

Since 2006 the museum has acquired thousands of new specimens, including a huge collection of fossils that had been held by the Civil and Environmental Engineering and Earth Sciences Department in 2012. Since 2006, the Hellenthals and their student workers have been working to maintain, organize, and catalog the existing collection in addition to their research, outreach, and classroom commitments.

Science students who frequent Jordan Hall might wonder why the museum is not more public-facing like the ones at Harvard, the University of Michigan, or UC Berkeley. Dr. Larson explained that, while growth is on the horizon, the museum's scope is currently limited by a small staff, the layout of the space, the lack of glass casing need-

ed to protect specimens, and limited funding.

Despite these challenges, Dr. Larson, who is set to take over as the primary museum curator when the Hellenthals retire, wants more people to have access to the museum's collection. She is currently working with the College of Science and the Department of Biological Sciences to add glass cases across the western wall of the Jordan Galleria and she is in the initial stages of acquiring models or skeletons to be hung from the Galleria ceiling. She is also working on creating databases of the collections, building an endowment for the museum, getting more classes and researchers to use the museum specimens, and creating informational displays for some of the visible specimens.

When asked what she would do with unlimited funding and support, Dr. Larson explained her dream for a brand new building which would include space for classrooms, research, outreach events, storage, a conservatory, and of course lots of informational and interactive exhibits about the natural sciences. There are no current plans for a new building, but she hopes that this new expansion will help get students, faculty, and alumni excited about the museum and everything it has to offer.

Because of the museum's limited staff, they are not able to stay open for student visitors as often as they would like, but they are open for game days during the fall semester and Dr. Larson and the Hellenthals offer tours upon request. If you are interested in a tour, using specimens for a class or your own research, or want to inquire about student employment or research opportunities, you can contact Dr. Larson or the Hellenthals by email.

Anthropology Research at ND and its Intersection with STEM

Christine Hruby, '26

When many people think of research, they typically imagine a lab bench, latex gloves, a centrifuge, or test tubes. However, the University of Notre Dame offers research opportunities for undergraduate students in many disciplines besides science. This leads me to introduce readers to Notre Dame's School Story Lab. Created by Professor Susan Blum, School Story Lab is an Anthropology Research Lab at the University of Notre Dame that compiles school stories from students across the world. The overall goal of the lab is to inform policymakers about factors that hinder a positive school experience in hopes that they can improve the education system. Undergraduate students interview students from around the world to hear about their experiences in education, upload a biweekly newsletter, and post student stories on the School Story Lab website (Schoolstorylab.com) and social media pages.

Although an Anthropology Lab, the undergraduates involved span many majors. For example, Iris Choi is a student in the lab who is majoring in ACMS and Economics. As such, School Story Lab serves as an opportunity for students like Iris to apply their data analysis and computational skills learned within the ACMS classroom to projects within Anthropology. During the beginning of this semester, Iris and the other undergraduate students are focusing on interviewing students worldwide. For example, Iris interviewed a student from Korea who explained her story about being a student in Korea. By the end of February, the researchers hope to compile around 24 new interviews. In the coming months, they plan to sort through all of the interviews to find common themes and trends. They plan to display the results on a

poster presentation at SARE, or the Student Anthropology Research Forum, this April.

Like Iris, I too plan to use my data analysis skills learned in the classroom to analyze the stories from the interviews and to visualize the data clearly for individuals to understand the results. As an Applied Computational Mathematics and Statistics Major (ACMS), I never thought that I could use the knowledge obtained from class towards a topic like Anthropology. As a result, being a part of this lab will provide me with the opportunity to gain better exposure to applying mathematical methods and other computational skills in the social science field.

Oppenheimer at ND: The Role of Notre Dame's Nuclear Science Laboratory in the Manhattan Project

Rose Hewald, '26

Starting with the operation of its first accelerator in 1938, The University of Notre Dame has been an instrumental player in nuclear science since the beginning of the field. Now home to The Huddle, Irish Gardens, and various dining options, LaFortune Student Center was previously the Science Hall and housed the second accelerator on campus. This 40-foot-long accelerator, known as the "Atom Smasher," was the largest in the country at the time and would play a key role in the Manhattan Project of World War II.

From its initial focus on using electron beams to its current concentration on accelerating heavier positively charged particles, Notre Dame's Nuclear Science Laboratory (NSL) has been a driving force and major contributor to nuclear astrophysics.

Because of its impressive design and ability to generate 4 million volts, the Atom Smasher was quickly commis-

sioned for wartime research after its completion in 1942. A team of scientists would commute to Notre Dame from the University of Chicago, using the same South Shore Line that many Notre Dame students use today, to use this accelerator for material radiation testing. Day-to-day operations included the help of two Notre Dame graduate students, and the group's goal was to produce plutonium.

The Atom Smasher (1941)

This collaboration was a part of the World War II Manhattan Project that is depicted in the 2023 blockbuster film *Oppenheimer*. Scientists for the project were largely concerned with ensuring that the bomb would not cause fusion in the atmosphere and ignite. To study this phenomenon, several other nuclear research facilities focused on understanding fusion, while Notre Dame studied the release of energy through fission and cooling through electron radiation emission. Together, these efforts led to the successful development of the first atomic bomb.

Bernie Waldman, Notre Dame Laboratory Director at the time, observed not only the bomb tests, but also the actual release of the Little Boy uranium bomb on Hiroshima on August 6, 1945, from an observation aircraft. Waldman returned to the University as it refocused on research of fundamental nuclear structure. He would go on to serve as Dean of the College of Science and stay with Notre Dame until his retirement in 1979.

The NSL is currently located in Nieuwland Science Hall and has been continuously operating since around 1970, making Notre Dame home to one of the nation's longest-operating accelerator laboratories at a university.

The current research is focused on using nuclear reactions to explore details of nuclear structure and reaction mechanisms by accelerating heavier positively charged particles. It is not only about studying nuclear reactions, but also the environments in which these processes

occur. When applied to the universe, these results can tell us about the evolution of a star, from birth to death, and ultimately about the evolution of the cosmos as a whole.

Notre Dame's NSL is still growing and remains a model for nuclear physics research across the world. Since 2012, its faculty has doubled, allowing students to get hands-on experience in various nuclear topics.

“We have flexibility [in our research] because our focus is diverse,” said Michael Weischer, Freimann Chair Professor of Physics and Director of the Institute for Structure and Nuclear Astrophysics (ISNAP) at the University of Notre Dame.

Today, some of the major research areas being explored in the NSL by students and faculty include Standard Model testing, accelerator mass spectrometry (AMS), capture reactions, the cluster structure of nuclei, and the evolution of nuclear structure. “They all ask different questions,” noted Weischer. These questions are answered using the instruments in the lab. The oldest and largest of these is the 10MV FN Tandem accelerator, where 10MV refers to the maximum terminal voltage of the instrument. In use since 1968, it creates a potential difference using a negatively charged ion source and is used for AMS. The Sta. ANA (Stable ion Accelerator for Nuclear Astrophysics) 5U 5MV accelerator was installed in 2012 and is used with the St. George recoil separator. This separator helps researchers study radiative captures using inverse kinematics reactions. The most recent NSL accelerator is the St. Andrew 3MV Tandem Accelerator, completed in 2017, and it is used for ion beam analysis.

Much like the research efforts of the 1940s, the NSL is in collaboration with other universities and laboratories today. For example, ISNAP is focused at Notre Dame, but it incorporates projects at the Michigan State University Facility of Radioactive Ion Beams (FRIB) and at Argonne National Laboratory.

Additionally, Notre Dame plays a role in the Compact Accelerator System for Performing Astrophysical Research (CASPAR) project. This 1MV electrostatic accelerator in South Dakota is located in an old gold mine 4850 ft underground and seeks to understand nuclear fusion reactions inside collapsing stars. This project is a collaboration between Notre Dame, the Sanford Underground Research Facility, and the South Dakota School of Mines and Technology.

This sense of cooperation and the expansive trove of resources available through the Notre Dame NSL has

facilitated its pivotal role in the nation's history, contributions to some of the most crucial developments to date in nuclear astrophysics, and maintenance of its status as one of the oldest university accelerator facilities in the country.

Civil and Environmental Engineering and Earth Sciences Field Trips

Quinn Mackay, '24

There are a lot of cool classes at Notre Dame, but some of the very best must be the Geology Field Trip courses offered every Fall and Spring break through the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering and Earth Sciences (CEEES). These field trips provide opportunities for undergraduates to see the geological and environmental processes they learn about in the classroom in the field—to apply their existing knowledge of geologic scenarios and understand how these concepts have caused the geographic landscape we see today.

Spring 2023 Field Trip to Big Bend National Park

Some of the recent destinations of these field trips include the Upper Peninsula of Michigan and the Galapagos Islands for Fall Break, and Big Bend National Park in Texas, Death Valley National Park in California, and the Big Island of Hawaii for Spring Break. Each of these locations provide world class geology and easy access. Notre Dame professors Dr. Jeremy Fein and Dr. Antonio Simone typically lead the Fall and Spring trips respectively, and students greatly benefit from their decades of expertise, and vast knowledge on geological topics.

As an Environmental and Earth Sciences major, I have had the opportunity so far to go on two of these trips myself, to the Upper Peninsula of Michigan in the Fall and

Big Bend National Park in the spring. The draw of these field trips extends beyond academics itself; they foster a sense of community and camaraderie among geologists, biologists, engineers, and environmental scientists. Students form lasting friendships over science without a worry of exams or grades, and bond over a day's shared adventures while marveling at a million stars on the border of Mexico. Whether hiking in 100° heat or watching fall foliage at sunset on the Keweenaw peninsula, these experiences create memories that push past the confines of the classroom. It's not just about studying geology; it's about embracing a lifestyle of appreciation for the Earth system, and a reminder that we chose the career paths we did.

If you have not had the opportunity to take a Geology field trip through CEEES, or any of the multitude of other field courses offered at Notre Dame (such as the Center for Social Concerns Appalachia seminar, SSLP, etc.), I urge you to consider it. We often forget the application of science when we spend all semester taking exams, and taking science or service into the 'real world' is a great way to remind yourself of the importance of what you are learning and renew your interest in the field.

Notre Dame Undergraduate Research at MD Anderson

Ina Satpathy, '27

This past summer, five Notre Dame students participated in a unique research opportunity at the MD Anderson Cancer Center. Located in Houston, TX, MD Anderson is one of the nation's top cancer care research centers and hospitals. The University of Notre Dame Summer Undergraduate Research Program at MD Anderson Cancer Center is a competitive, ten-week program designed for brilliant and motivated students pursuing a career in medicine or research. The program offers students mentorship, hands-on laboratory experience, and insight into the scientific world.

Current junior Sisy Chen reflected on her experiences there as a very positive and educational opportunity. She appreciated the chance to dive into a new field of study as she worked in the

Sood Lab researching ovarian cancer and metastasis. Not only did she gain hands-on experience and develop her laboratory skills, she was "part of a brilliant community of scientists and researchers" that she continues to collaborate with today.

Another participant of the research program was Josiah Miller who was part of the Amit Lab studying cancer biology and neuroscience. He worked on innovating research surrounding Psilocybin, the psychoactive drug in magic mushrooms, to determine if the drug could cause neurogenesis effects which would lengthen the nerve endings and potentially protect them against oral cancers that limit patients' ability to swallow. In a wonderful conclusion to the summer, he was one of the winners of the poster competition and allowed his lab to get recognition for breakthrough research in the field.

Overall, this partnership introduced students to the scientific research world and enabled them to see the progression of their own work. It was a vital experience that will prove useful in their future research and medical careers.

Artificial Intelligence, Real Solutions: How a Telehealth Tool Is Being Used to Revolutionize Pediatric Oncology in Mexico

Julia Marine, '24

When you think of artificial intelligence, what comes to mind? You may consider emotionless machines like robots, Apple's Siri or Amazon's Alexa, science-fiction media such as "Black Mirror," or natural language processing tools like ChatGPT. For Notre Dame's Dr. Angélica García Martínez, AI has a very unique and personal importance. She is the driving force behind HealthApp-MD, an AI-based tool that is revolutionizing the pediatric oncology system in one of Mexico's most prevalent pediatric hospitals.

Dr. García Martínez hails from Mexico City. There, she grew up and attended the Universidad Iberoamericana, Ciudad de México, where she received a Bachelor of Sciences in Nutrition and Food Science. Dr. García Martínez later earned her Ph.D. in Public Health and Epidemiology from the National Institute of Public Health in Mexico, her research exploring the association between exposure to heavy metals and human breast cancer incidence. Dr. García Martínez's passionate interest in public health led her to pursue community work. She served as a Research Director for Un Kilo de Ayuda, a transformational NGO that addresses the needs of children in indigenous Mexican rural areas. Within her position, she developed a system called INFOKilo v.2.1 which addresses the persistent anemia and malnutrition she observed in children of these communities. With the help of Dr. Nitesh Chawla, she also created a system that uses GPS technology to refer children in these rural areas to specific hospitals based on their current health conditions.

Dr. García Martínez's research addresses an emergent and under-studied issue within the oncology department at the Hospital Infantil de México Federico Gómez (HIMFG) in Mexico City. Cancer is a disease that causes significant mortality amongst Mexico's children and teenagers, with 156.9 pediatric cases per million as of 2012 (Monárrez et al. 2022). Pediatric patients who have completed their chemotherapy treatments are routinely released from the hospital's care, but due to the invasive

nature of the treatment, they are particularly susceptible to medical complications such as bacteremia, persistent neutropenia, bleeding, septic shock and death. Often, pediatric patients and their families do not possess adequate health insurance and do not have access to medical literacy resources. Families may sometimes live long distances from the HIMFG and prefer to stay around the hospital while their child is receiving treatment, resorting to sleeping on the street outside of the hospital. As a result, children with cancer and their caregivers are a particularly vulnerable population in Mexico.

A solution to these issues lies in HealthApp-MD, a tool developed by Dr. García Martínez and the Lucy Family Institute at Notre Dame. The primary goals of the app are to help health personnel, families, and caregivers resolve the needs of children who have finished undergoing chemotherapy treatments and to improve healthcare access for these children. All features of the app are accessible at no cost to pediatric oncology patients, their caregivers, and the hospital staff at HIMFG.

HealthApp-MD is composed of two main apps. The first of these is the Mobile App, which is accessible by caretakers of children with cancer. The Mobile App interface allows caregivers to track their child's signs and symptoms, prompting them to do so every few hours. The app's algorithm evaluates the child's medical state based on the alarm generated by certain signs and symptoms. If these symptoms change significantly, the app will alert the caregiver to contact HIMFG staff for further instructions. Additionally, the Mobile App collects data regarding the child's social determinants of healthcare access, such as their education level and their family's economic stability. These are important factors to consider alongside their medical symptoms.

The second component of the app is the Web App, which is accessible by health personnel at HIMFG. This tool aims to consolidate the medical files within a pediatric oncology patient's file. As these children get shuffled through the healthcare system, the number of documents pertaining to them can accumulate and become disorganized. The consolidation of these files by the app's algorithm allows doctors to gain a holistic image of the child's medical history and current medical state, as it is reported by caregivers using the app at home. In this way, the Web App acts as a simple yet necessary improvement to the organization of pediatric oncology patient data at HIMFG.

Another major goal of HealthApp-MD is to provide a

support system for caregivers. Cancer is traumatic not only for the children who are diagnosed with it but also for families and caregivers of pediatric oncology patients. Many of these individuals display acute mental health disease symptoms as a result of newfound financial, personal, and emotional distress. Recognizing this, Dr. García Martínez implemented a mental health support feature within HealthApp-MD. Caregivers are able to complete gold-standard mental health surveys through the app, which are then received and analyzed by the Department of Psychology at the HIMFG. If the psychology specialists determine that a caregiver has a significant number of risk factors associated with conditions such as depression or anxiety, the caregiver will be contacted by the department and referred to a specialist who can provide them with mental health support. This feature of HealthApp-MD addresses a growing mental health crisis which is only exacerbated by childhood cancer.

While the app is almost fully developed, with a cohort of over 275 families involved in the study to date, Dr. García Martínez and her team are working on launching a new phase of the app that will address certain limitations of the program. Families facing unfamiliarity with downloading and using phone apps is one of the main barriers to the success of HealthApp-MD. Dr. García Martínez believes that the solution lies in creating algorithms that will increase the user-friendliness of the app. She also intends for the app to create and foster an educational community by increasing the health literacy of families. In this way, caretakers can better understand the importance of resolving chemotherapy-related health issues in their children and support each other in utilizing the app's features.

Dr. García Martínez's experience working at Notre Dame has been "extraordinary." She extended her thanks for the hard work of Notre Dame Ph.D. students and the Interdisciplinary Traineeship for Socially Responsible and Engaged Data Scientists (iTREDS) scholars, a group of Notre Dame and St. Mary's College Students involved in developing different components of the HealthApp-MD tool and helping with data analysis. She also expressed special gratitude to Dr. Chawla, who played an integral role in developing the app and provided Dr. García Martínez with facilities and support.

Dr. García Martínez is still developing HealthApp-MD and is excited to see how this trailblazing application of AI will change to benefit pediatric oncology patients and their families. She hopes the project will continue to evolve to meet the needs of this vulnerable community of children and families in Mexico, and she sees the project's

presence at Notre Dame as an opportunity for students to develop their ability to connect to the needs of others. In her words, "This small seed that we are planting now is potentially going to create a beautiful garden. I'm talking in a metaphoric way, but these are the kind of good things that change the world."

The family interface of HealthApp-MD, showing a survey assessing the family member's social determinants of health. Courtesy of Dr. Angélica García Martínez.

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Using RNA to Recreate Life: Dr. DasGupta's Research into the Origins of Life on Earth

Alura D'Souza, '25

Where does life come from? An ancient question still pondered today by both the philosopher and citizen alike. For new Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry faculty member Dr. Saurja DasGupta, this daunting question has captivated his attention at both the intellectual and philosophical levels. As Dr. DasGupta puts it, “the fact that life started from nonliving matter, from scratch, sounds almost unbelievable. But if we think about it, a lot of complex things start from scratch—like [a newborn child] learning a language.” Utilizing biochemistry, Dr. DasGupta aims to travel back in time to reconstruct the “crime scene” that led to the emergence of life on Earth. Using chemical and biochemical processes believed to be prevalent on ancient Earth, he works to recreate the primordial conditions in his own lab with the goal to “break down a living cell into its fundamental components, learn the chemical grammar, and then put those components together in a biologically meaningful way.”

Scientists speculate that life evolved approximately 4 billion years ago. This primitive life was likely very different compared to the living organisms present today. In the current understanding of life, all living organisms are

composed of cells and require two crucial components: genes and enzymes. Genes act as biological blueprints for cells, encoding for enzymes which carry out roles essential to cellular survival and function. Life today utilizes DNA to perform genetic functions and proteins to perform enzymatic functions, but this poses the paradoxical question of which came first: DNA or proteins? Perhaps, instead, a single molecule could act as an enzyme and perform functions within the cell, in addition to being able to evolve, carry, and pass on its genetic information. This is where RNA and Dr. DasGupta's research comes in. While more commonly known as a messenger molecule in cells, RNA can act as both genes and enzymes. This suggests that perhaps the earliest forms of life on Earth used RNA as both their genetic material and enzymes.

Prior to joining Notre Dame, Dr. DasGupta completed his postdoctoral research at Harvard Medical School. There, he worked to replicate primordial systems by resurrecting extinct enzymatic RNA molecules likely used by primordial cells. He used a technique called *in vitro* evolution, which allows researchers to generate RNA molecules with desired functions. This is achieved by challenging a large group of RNA molecules with the task of performing the desired function, and then selectively isolating the sequences best at performing that function. These isolated sequences are then amplified and subjected to continuous rounds of screening with either increasing stringency or different conditions used, until the most active RNA molecules for that desired function are isolated. Using this technique, Dr. DasGupta identified a suite of RNA enzymes that were likely important for early life. Through the incorporation of these RNA enzymes into liposome-based models of primordial cells, known as protocells, Dr. DasGupta investigated their activity within cell-like environments. Comparing the function of the RNA enzymes within the protocells and extracellularly, he found that the enzymes functioned just as well in the cell-like environment.

Currently, utilizing his artificial evolution platform, Dr. DasGupta desires to continue studying the mechanisms of how primordial RNA molecules evolved. Carrying out evolutionary experiments at the molecular level will allow Dr. DasGupta to infer the evolutionary mechanisms that allow RNA sequences to acquire new functions. As Dr. DasGupta says, “the ability to evolve molecules at will that perform any desired biochemical function, including those not present in nature, opens up exciting possibilities in fundamental research, diagnostics, and therapeutics.” His hope is that his lab will be able to utilize these evolutionary approaches to create a self-replicating RNA molecule, or a self-replicase, something that has yet to be

recreated by researchers. Through the integration of these RNA enzymes, including a self-replicase, into protocells, Dr. DasGupta expects the protocells to exhibit various lifelike behaviors including cellular growth, division, competition, and the ability to evolve spontaneously, bringing the DasGupta Lab one step closer to unlocking the secrets of life itself.

Study Abroad and Science: Hand in Hand

Lindsay Barrow, '25

In the Institute of International Education's 2022 report, Notre Dame was ranked second in the nation for study abroad participation, with a participation rate of 77% of undergraduate students during the 2021-2022 school year. Michael Pippenger, Vice President and Associate Provost for Internationalization sees this recognition as a tribute to the University's commitment to inspiring future leaders to explore and experience other cultures and learn beyond the United States. The link between study abroad and career development seems obvious for those in the humanities, but this opportunity for worldly leadership and collaboration is one that highly pertains to students in the College of Science.

Of the 188,753 U.S. students who received academic credit for study abroad in 2021-22, 252 institutions reported that 12,697 students participated in non-credit experiential activities, such as work, internships, volunteering, and research abroad (Open Doors Report). Several Notre Dame College of Science students have well captured the variety of experience that can be found to personalize their experiences abroad, engaging with their country beyond their coursework.

Member of the Class of 2025 and Science Pre-Professional Studies major Katie Krause found an independent research experience in the Department of Infectious Disease at Imperial College London. Malaria is prominent in the United Kingdom due to a large portion of the population visiting areas of Africa over the summer holiday. Katie worked closely with Dr. Aubrey Cunnington and Dr. Stefan Ebmeier on their SCRIPT Malaria study, a clinical trial which tracks the recovery of individuals with the Malaria infection. Their work informs drug development by improving and speeding recovery. Katie reflects emphasizing her gratitude for the opportunity to gain insights on the underpinnings of a clinical trial as well as the research process and healthcare system in the

United Kingdom.

Notre Dame alumna Aidan Crowley is currently pursuing an M.D.-Ph.D. at the University of Pennsylvania Perelman School of Medicine and Wharton School of Business. A member of Notre Dame's Class of 2021, Aidan studied abroad in Copenhagen, Denmark, her junior fall. During her semester abroad, she worked with faculty from the University of Copenhagen to study shared decision-making (SDM) in Denmark versus in the U.S. Aidan worked closely with a team at Mayo Clinic to analyze unhurried conversations in the clinical encounter. Aidan connected her understanding of SDM in different health systems with the science of compassion, her minor while at Notre Dame. This experience has informed Aidan's current research as an M.D.-Ph.D. in Health Care Management and Economics to study how health system structure influences job identity of the clinician workforce.

Catherine Chung, a Class of 2025 Science Pre-Professional Studies and English student, participated in the Kennedy Scholar Program during her time in the London Undergraduate Program. The Kennedy Scholar program connected Catherine with a rich range of research locations around London as well as mentorship from UK-based academics. This enabled Catherine to further her Honors Senior Thesis researching generational trauma induced by the institution of slavery and the role of writing as a form of healing from individual and generational trauma. Catherine's research on trauma and healing is incredibly relevant to her goal of pursuing a career in medicine. Catherine weaves her English major as well as themes from her Compassionate Care in Medicine minor. Catherine's research is an excellent example of the blend of science and humanities research abroad. Lastly, participating in the Kennedy Scholar program allowed her to engage further with the research community in the United Kingdom.

As Notre Dame continues to establish itself as a top-tier study abroad institution, it's fascinating to observe the synergy between science and international education, with many College of Science students customizing and personalizing their experiences.

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Notre Dame Illuminates Colorful Light for Rare Disease Awareness

Kayla Nguyen, '24

“Green, Blue, Pink and Purple are the colors of unity for all those impacted by rare diseases and the different colors represent the diversity of people that are affected,” says Barbara Calhoun, director of the Advocacy, Education, and Outreach Initiative for rare diseases in the College of Science. This year, Leap Day on February 29th means a lot more to the rare disease community than an extra day, as it is also International Rare Disease Day for 2024. Every year, many buildings around the world illuminate colors of the rare disease community by showing support for those affected by rare disease. The College of Science, Hesburgh Library, the Boler-Parseghian Center for Rare and Neglected Diseases, and the Patient Advocacy Initiative at the University of Notre Dame are the organizations behind the work of raising awareness on campus. The Notre Dame community joined together on February 29th to #LightUpForRare at the Word of Life mural on Hesburgh Library with a brief blessing by Father Pete McCormick.

“It is a day dedicated to raising awareness about rare diseases and their impact on patients and their families.

It is a day to unify in advocating for medical research and policy changes to improve care and access to treatments,” says Calhoun. “The rare disease community embodies the strength and tenacity to face challenges that are often overlooked by the broader public. This community is a testament to the power of collective advocacy, support, and research in driving forward progress and innovation in healthcare.”

Rare diseases can be classified as those that affect fewer than 200,000 people in the United States according to the National Organization for Rare Disorders (NORD). As stated by the National Institutes of Health (NIH), there are approximately 7,000 rare diseases. Of the known rare diseases, it is predicted that 95% have no treatment. The Notre Dame Minor in Science and Patient Advocacy (MSPA) has created many initiatives to bring awareness

to the rare disease community, many of which came to light on Rare Disease Day.

Calvin Hawe, a senior minoring in Science and Patient Advocacy, described how the

lighting of the colored light for #LightUpForRare is a hopeful symbol for the rare disease community. “Rare Disease Day is an important day for myself and everyone else to take a step back and recognize the obstacles faced by people living with rare diseases, and then formulate tangible plans to support these patients to the best of our abilities,” he said. For him, illuminating the colorful lights for Rare Disease Day provided reinforcement of his desire to make a positive contribution to this community by supporting the development of innovative novel treatments and consistently advocating for patients.

Students in the MSPA minor worked hard to raise awareness through campus awareness campaigns, such as tabling at dining halls, hanging posters, advertising on TV screens, as well as community outreach through social media messaging, Calhoun says. Katrina Conrad, Program Manager for the Advocacy Education and Outreach Initiative & Minor in Science and

Patient Advocacy, worked with Calhoun to organize the Rare Disease Day events on campus, including the 15th Annual Conference on Advancing Rare Disease Research. “Our awareness campaigns are working as we are expecting more participants at our event and conference than ever before.”

It can feel isolating to have a diagnosis that most others don't understand, so having a day where all of the rare community can find support through each other and to have their voices uplifted is empowering, says Marin Kalista, a senior minoring in Science and Patient Advocacy with plans to get her Masters in Genetic Counseling after graduating. “For me, the lighting ceremony also represents how important advocacy work is: this event is being put on by some incredible people in our program who have worked really hard to ensure the voices of rare patients are heard and appreciated - to see the work we do on a daily basis culminate into this massive campus-wide event is really special.”

Female Physician Burnout in Relation to Work Life Balance

Lily Freda, '24

Over one third of all active physicians in our country are women, who navigate unique challenges in medicine (7). By choosing medicine, females undertake far more considerations than their male counterparts when making decisions for their future. In today's world, there is no emotional or physical support system for women who strive to go into medicine and also raise a family. There is limited support for the journey a woman's body must go through during pregnancy or after birth. Although maternity leave varies depending on location and job, there

is little to no consideration of the mental and physical toll that having a child takes on a woman. In the medical field, bearing a child is often seen as a setback. Because of this, a large percentage of female physicians put off having children until their careers become more stable, thus increasing the possible risks during pregnancy. The majority of issues surrounding female burnout in medicine can be attributed to the struggle with their work-life balance.

Burnout can be defined as a psychological syndrome of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment that occurs among individuals who work with other people in some capacity. All physicians have the propensity to suffer from burnout, however, it is 60% higher in female physicians than in male physicians. Burnout can be related to the discrepancies in suicide rates between genders. Male physicians were found to have a lower rate of suicide than non-physicians, while female physicians were found to have higher rates of suicide than non-physicians (9). In order to ensure that the people who take care of others for a living are in fact taken care of themselves, everyone must understand the possibly life-threatening results of burnout.

Many of the results of burnout in female physicians stem from the unfortunate coincidence that opportune childbearing years directly overlap with the most strenuous part of medical training. In 2018, the average age of a medical school student was 24, indicating that a significant number of all new physicians finish their medical training in their mid-thirties. Any pregnancy after the age of 35 is considered to have increased risks and complications in addition to an increase in infertility. As of 2019, 25% of female physicians were found to struggle with fertility and 42% of female surgeons were also reported to have fertility issues, as well as an increase in pregnancy loss. These numbers, when compared to the 10% of non-physician females diagnosed with infertility issues, demonstrate the direct correlation between difficulty having a family and being a female in the medical field (9).

Beyond problems with fertility, the course of pregnancy is made much more arduous when working in medicine. By the time that a female physician's career allows her the time to start a family, the concerns for a pregnant woman over the age of 35 emerge. These concerns include restricted fetal growth, preterm labor, placental abruption, preeclampsia, miscarriages, and stillbirth (9). Due to the nature of pregnancy, women are tasked with the complex decision of whether to wait to start a family or to wreak

havoc on their career by becoming pregnant early into training. To delve deeper, both decisions to the previous predicament can be considered. If a female physician decides to wait until after their intense training to have a child, there will be inevitable risks for the mother and child. If a female physician decides instead to have a child during training, she truncates her medical career (6). Clearly, her career becomes stifled by two different elements in her life: work and family.

A study in Spain during the years 2005-2014 shows the rates of suicide per 100,000 deaths in non-physicians vs physicians, demonstrating the discrepancy between male and female physician suicide rates (4).

The challenges inherent in balancing work and family responsibilities for female physicians are further complicated by the realities of maternity leave, which typically ranges from 6 to 8 weeks. The minimum amount of time for postpartum recovery is 6 weeks, no matter how the baby is delivered. One study demonstrated that the 6-8 duration of maternity leave is not enough. Out of 844 women physicians in the United States who were surveyed, 73.3% reported that leave time provided was not sufficient. Eighty-nine percent stated that they would have preferred a time ranging from 11 weeks to 6 months. The study also explored back-to-work experiences. The most negative experiences when returning to work revolved around the lack of facilities for breast pumping, minimal time for breast pumping, difficulty finding childcare and maternal discrimination (5).

Furthermore, maternal bias is another obstacle that female physicians may encounter at work. A study in 2017 by the University of California San Francisco (UCFS) studied 6,000 physician mothers about the biases they

experienced firsthand while working. 66.3% of women reported gender discrimination, with 35.8% specifically reporting gender discrimination centered around their pregnancies. Most of the discrimination these women felt due to their pregnancies revolved around maternity leave and time spent breastfeeding. The author of this study, Eleni Linos, M.D., an assistant professor of medicine at UCSF, stated, "Physician mothers treat patients, raise children, teach students and care for sick relatives and friends. But who looks after them? We need to make sure these women get fair and unbiased treatment at the workplace" (2). Linos astutely captured the essence of why physician mothers are deserving of a welcoming workplace.

From a family standpoint, female physicians encounter setbacks because they were found more likely to cut back on work in order to maintain household duties. In fact, physician mothers were calculated to spend at least nine more hours each week completing domestic tasks than their male counterparts. Women are even more likely to cancel a full day of work if their child is ill or if school has a day off. In 2018, a study was published on 1,712 attending physician mothers exploring their lives at home. Of these attending physicians, 99.2% of them were married or had a permanent partner. These women were asked how many household tasks they were responsible for at home. Some examples of tasks would be doing laundry, doing the dishes, or scheduling child-care. Of the mothers studied, 32% of those who were tasked with fewer than five household duties reported that they would be interested in a career change. Comparatively, if mothers oversaw more than five household duties, the amount of those women who would be interested in switching careers jumped to 55% (8). If physician mothers are tasked with handling their strenuous job and a strenuous number of duties at home, burnout is inevitable.

Even with the numerous challenges that female physicians face, there are a multitude of potential solutions. A starting point for tangible change could focus on fertility, implementing insurance policies to support fertility treatments and ensuring that these treatments are accessible to female physicians. Increasing paid maternity leave time and introducing benefits to bolster new families after the birth of their child would allow for women to have a child earlier in their career, without facing the fear of a low income and difficulty adjusting back into work. Women could be given sufficient time to breast pump and a safe environment in which to do so in order to feel more comfortable feeding their child. As

compared to dropping a child off at a secondary location, on-site childcare could be immensely helpful to female physicians, helping to coordinate their busy schedules and save travel time (9). Additionally, mentorship and interventional counseling could be useful tools for any expecting mother, particularly those who have fast-paced careers. Therapy or any form of counseling could prepare pregnant women with views of what their new life will look like once a child is in the picture. In addition, it would be a safe environment to voice fears. Counseling could then be continued after the birth to bolster women with postpartum depression, anxiety, managing a minimal amount of sleep, and even body image issues (3). The goal of these solutions is to ensure that no one in the medical field must choose between becoming a doctor or becoming a parent.

The postpartum timeline including physical recovery and returning to work.

One program working towards finding solutions to meet the diverse needs of women in healthcare is The Women's Wellness through Equity and Leadership (WEL) project. WEL was formed in 2018 by six healthcare organizations "focused on bringing together early- to mid-career women physicians for networking, mentorship and leadership training." WEL has progressed to now being composed of ten healthcare organizations who have vowed to focus on helping the next generation of female physicians to "build a healthier, more equitable work experience." Women are selected from the ten organizations to participate and are provided with a curriculum centered around well-being, equity, and leadership. The hope is that these women take the activities learned in the 18-month program and apply them to their practice and/or lives. The program has rave reviews and is said to be a "sisterhood of support" (1). There is something to be said for finding strength in numbers, particularly when a support team is such an essential part of easing the obstacles women face in medicine. We not only need more programs like this to be developed, but we need them to be inclusive in recruiting more members.

Female physicians today and all future generations of female physicians deserve an equal chance for success

and prosperity in their careers. Physician mothers face the challenging balance of waiting to start a family and increasing the pregnancy risks or becoming pregnant early into training and stifling their career. To combat this difficult choice, the medical system must reconcile by aiding physician mothers. Such adjustments include assistance in fertility struggles, maternal leave, increased on-site childcare, and supportive programs. If, and only if, these plans come to fruition, will there be less burnout for female physicians and therefore, more equality in the medical field.

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The Release of Human Pathogens from the Melting Ice

by Alura D'Souza '25

ABSTRACT

As a consequence of climate change, the release rate of cryospheric ice melt is increasing. With the incorporation of this meltwater into ecosystems comes the incorporation of a plethora of microbes. Numerous entrapped pathogenic and non-pathogenic microbes have previously been identified frozen within the ice; however, the impact these microbes will have within ecosystems and on human health upon their release from the cryosphere is unknown. Current research into these microbes, including mechanisms of their long-term cryogenic survivability and the consequences of their release, or the release of their genetic material, is significantly lacking. This review aims to provide a brief investigation into the current knowledge pertaining to potential human pathogens entrapped within the cryosphere, with a focus on bacteria and viruses, in order to provide information pertaining to the health consequences their release may have.

INTRODUCTION

Frozen water on the Earth's surface, including sea ice, ice caps, glaciers, and the permafrost, are components of the cryosphere that act as a reservoir for a multitude of microbes.^{1,2} The density of microorganisms in glaciers alone is quite high, at approximately $10^2 - 10^7$ cells per mL of glacier ice.³ Microbes can be harbored in clouds and fog, and once airborne, carried over distances to become incorporated into cryosphere ice via landing on the glacial surface or precipitation.^{4,2} Organic and inorganic debris may also entrap microbes and deposit them into the cryosphere.⁵ Additionally, the presence of frozen microbes within the cryosphere can be attributed to accompanying frozen carcasses of dead organisms.⁶

With the high density of microbes in the cryosphere, rising global temperatures have consequences that should not be overlooked. Over the span of approximately twenty years (1994 – 2017), around 28 trillion tons of global ice were lost, largely due to climate change.⁷ Within a liter of environmental ice meltwater, Rogers et al. summarized there to be $10^3 - 10^7$ viable microbes present. Due to current climate conditions, microbial release rates will likely increase, and with it, an increase in annual rates of viable frozen microbes released into the environment.²

HUMAN PATHOGENS FOUND WITHIN POLAR ICE

A large variety of different microbes have been identified in ice samples.³ Within subglacial habitats, the presence of tinea nigra causing *Hortaea werneckii*, a species of black yeast, was found.⁸ In looking at cultured bacterial isolates taken from polar habitats within the Arctic archipelago, Mongrovejo-Aries et al. found that many of these isolates exhibited hemolytic activity and had bacterial species closely related to them capable of producing cytolytic and cytotoxic compounds, including

pore-forming compounds.⁹ In water and glacial ice samples collected in the late 1990s, the presence of viable undetermined Enterobacter, Yersinia, and Klebsiella spp., among other coliforms, were observed, with some of the isolates demonstrating naturally occurring resistance to antibiotics, including cefazolin, ampicillin, and cefamandole, raising concerns about potential arctic superbugs.¹⁰

Among viruses found within the cryosphere, data supporting the occurrence of temporal gene flow in influenza A viruses via migrating birds was collected in Siberia lakes.¹¹ Other potential virus strains harbored within the ice are caliciviruses and poliovirus.¹² Additionally, the uncovering of frozen corpses of disease victims may serve to be a reservoir for pathogens. Traces of notable human bacterial and viral pathogens including *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus anthracis*, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *Mycobacterium leprae*, *Vibrio cholerae*, *Yersinia pestis*, and smallpox have been identified preserved within mummies, highlighting the potential for cryosphere melting to expose buried disease victims infected with ancient or especially dangerous pathogens.^{13,14,15} A demonstration of this was observed with the 2016 *B. anthracis* outbreak in Siberia, where the melting permafrost uncovered previously frozen *B. anthracis* spores believed to be from an uncovered carcass, which led to the infection of hundreds of reindeer and one human death.⁶ As with *B. anthracis*, bacterial pathogens of concern should include spore-forming species due to microbial dormancy prolonging bacteria survivability within the cryosphere. Spore-forming bacteria appear to dominate ice samples no older than 33,000 years; non-spore forming bacterial species are more prevalent in samples that are older. This suggests a need for metabolic activity and DNA repair after prolonged periods of time to retain viability.¹⁶

RETENTION OF VIABILITY IN FROZEN PATHOGENS

Retention of viability in frozen microbes differs between bacteria and viruses. The cryosphere is a hostile environment for non-psychrophilic bacteria with low temperatures, little nutrients, and high exposure to ultraviolet (UV) radiation.³ Over years of radiation exposure, breakages in bacterial DNA accumulate. This DNA may no longer retain functionality, especially if the breaks are double-stranded. Researchers at the Louisiana State University Department of Biological Sciences identified a psychrophilic "worker" enzyme that repairs DNA under metabolically low, freezing conditions, which may be similarly examined in non-psychrophilic bacteria counterparts.¹⁷ Evidence that non-psychrophilic bacteria are able to survive being frozen for thousands of years was obtained, showing that cellular metabolic activity and DNA repair pathways may help to confer long-term survivability while frozen in the cryosphere, with these mechanisms potentially offering additional or better methods of viability retention compared to dormancy.¹⁸

Since they are non-living, viruses may have an advantage over bacteria at viability retention. Some viruses are able to survive frozen within their host, such as the *Acanthamoeba* infecting

Pithovirus sibericum that was revived from 30,000-year-old samples from the Siberian permafrost.¹⁹ Others can abiotically survive in the cryosphere environment.²⁰ Between DNA and RNA viruses, RNA viruses have been hypothesized to survive better and have more infectivity due to their high mutagenic characteristics, allowing easier adaptation to new hosts and environments.¹² The ability of these microbes to be preserved within the cryosphere for thousands of years is concerning as ancient microbes may present a greater threat than their modern counterparts. The passage of time may serve to remove infection barriers ancient microbial hosts accumulated, creating increased infection rates by ancient microbes in modern hosts.²

FROM CRYOSPHERE MELTWATER TO HUMAN HOSTS

As postulated by Rogers et al. in 2004, if certain conditions were met, microbes could propagate through the ice via the cycle of “genome recycling.” Genome recycling is based on the idea that glaciers entrap a mixture of modern and ancient species’ genomes acquired via microbial transport through the hydrosphere. Once no longer entrapped within the ice, if a microbe possesses sufficient population size, has stable genes, and is able to propagate due to favorable environmental conditions, transportation, and allele fitness, members of its population can then once again become entrapped within the ice.²

Additionally, upon release, microbe interaction with native population causes gene flow.¹¹ Incorporation of ancestral alleles may increase modern microbes’ fitness through life cycle extension or environmental endurance capacity augmentation.² Even if the entrapped microbe fails to retain viability, free floating genetic material in meltwater may harbor risks. Antibiotic resistant genes (ARGs) in cryosphere samples and, as discussed by Yarzabal et al., the presence of bacteria that carry integrons—genes allowing the transfer of ARGs between bacteria—pose as health threats resulting from the possibility of modern bacteria acquiring novel ARGs.^{21,3}

Meltwater, animals, and the wind can serve to transport microbes to new habitats, allowing released ARGs to be encountered by a wide variety of bacterial species.^{22,2} Additionally, if the transported microbes are viable and they encounter the proper nutrients and environmental conditions, they have the capacity to grow, reproduce, and cause infections in susceptible human hosts. Much of the meltwater will end up in lakes, rivers, and oceans.² For some bacterial species, deposition into the oceans may be fatal; however, others are unaffected or even thrive in saline environments.²³ In populated areas near the permafrost, human pathogens may not have to be transported far in order to encounter a suitable host, increasing the possibility of an outbreak.^{3,22}

Smith et al. took the idea of genome recycling one step further and applied the hypothesis to viruses’ ability to be recycled through ice, contingent upon them being abundant, easily incorporated into the cryospheric ice, and upon release, causing continuous disease cycles. Released viruses, such as

RNA viruses with higher genetic variability, may be more likely to cause human infections due to the high volume of variants allowing adaptation to different environments. Animal to human pathogen infections could also arise, with model pathogens including RNA marine caliciviruses, a group of primarily ocean viruses with numerous infections of land animals, including humans, through ocean spray. These viruses have been observed to disappear for years, then rise again, a phenomenon that can be explained through their incorporation into cryosphere ice. Hosts include migratory whales, which can help to facilitate the spread of the virus, allowing it to jump to human hosts.¹²

Recently, in light of the COVID-19 pandemic and arctic wildfires, researchers Hofmeister et al. developed a model that explains how a major respiratory virus pandemic (MRVP) can originate from the melting permafrost, which they speculated in 2021 could be the origins of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. In their model, upon being freed from entrapment within the ice due to the melting summer permafrost, the virus is transported to the North Polar atmospheric cell by wind. Amidst intense UV-radiation exposure, the virus remains protected due to winter wildfires releasing organic aerosols into the atmosphere. As the North Polar cell extends to further latitudes during colder months, the warmer southern air creates liquid droplets, with the virus suspended inside. If the virus is present in high enough quantities and encounters a susceptible population, infection and a subsequent MRVP can emerge as a result of virus-containing rain droplets.²⁴

POSSIBLE ENVIRONMENTAL CONTAMINATION OF ICE CORE SAMPLES

Microbes have the second largest distribution of biomass on the planet, and as such, one limitation of the data gathered possibly exaggerates the quantity of microbes detected due to sample contamination.²⁵ Lab techniques take great care to reduce risks of contamination through protocols such as the washing of ice samples with ethanol frequently; however, these techniques are not perfect. Only bacteria, and not endospores, are killed in the ethanol-washing decontamination method, and this technique may fail to destroy nucleic acids present in samples.⁵ Additionally, the efficiency of techniques to remove viral contaminants was only recently evaluated.²⁶ Because of this, there may be a discrepancy in the viability of microbes detected within the samples and the microbes actually present. However, prior to 2000, only one instance of bacterial contamination (from a relative of the spore-forming *Bacillus subtilis*) was recorded on ethanol treated ice-core samples.⁵ Going forward, Zhong et al. developed and optimized a new decontamination method in 2021 that resulted in no DNA detection using nested PCR, and they were able to decontaminate the samples from viruses.²⁶ Using this technique in future experiments will provide researchers increased assurance in the accuracy of data gathered.

CONCLUSION

The cryosphere serves as a reservoir for many microbes, both known and unknown. As the ice entrapping these microbes melts, they have the ability to disseminate throughout the world via the hydrosphere or organismal host transport. The consequences of the release of both microbes and their genetic material needs to be considered. Resistance to antibiotics is rapidly increasing, and with meltwater adding additional or novel ARGs and integrons, the presence of resistant pathogens, or superbugs, may increase.²⁷ To date, with the exception of the 2016 Siberian anthrax outbreak, no definitive record of human infection from released microbes could be found; however, this does not mean cases have not occurred, nor should it be indicative of the future potential for released microbes to cause infection in human hosts. Events for encounters with released microbes can include exposure to contaminated water, interactions with infected organisms, or direct exposure, leading to a potential disease outbreak from released pathogens.^{12,24} With much still unknown about the species of microbes encased within the ice, the threat these microbes may pose to human health is difficult to evaluate. As climate change continues to lead to increased annual outputs of cryosphere meltwater, the importance and need to understand the effects releasing entrapped microbes will have on human health cannot be underscored. Future research efforts should serve to continue documenting viable microbes preserved within the cryosphere and evaluating their potential for human infection.

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Effect of Land Cover on the Estimated Risk of Tick-Borne Pathogens in Belize, Central America

by Grace Steffen ^{1,2,5}

ABSTRACT

Land cover changes frequently occur from extraction of natural resources, human population expansion, and natural disasters. Such environmental alterations can increase the risk of arthropod-borne diseases, including those transmitted by ticks. Knowledge on the influence of land cover change and risk of tick-borne diseases is limited. Commonly known as the “brown dog tick,” *Rhipicephalus linnaei* is considered the most widespread tick species in the world and represents an important vector of pathogens that cause human diseases such as Rocky Mountain Spotted Fever, Anaplasmosis, and Ehrlichiosis. The current study aimed to quantify and associate land cover change linked to deforestation with presence of *R. linnaei* in Belize, Central America. Adult ticks were collected from animal hosts in San Lazaro and Indian Church communities of the Orange Walk district in January 2020. Deforestation within a 200 km circumference of each community was characterized by quantifying the change in forested areas over a 5-year period (2017-2022) using satellite imagery. Results indicated a higher presence of *R. linnaei* in San Lazaro (91.5%) compared to Indian Church (77.2%), associated with an increased level of deforestation in San Lazaro (31.2%) compared to Indian Church (4.6%). These findings can contribute to the knowledge of tick-borne disease risk in Belize for greater public health awareness and help guide tick control campaigns for at-risk communities.

INTRODUCTION

Ticks are blood-sucking arthropods that parasitize most groups of terrestrial or semi-aquatic vertebrates and are important vectors of global public health concern.¹ *Rhipicephalus linnaei*, the tropical lineage of *Rhipicephalus sanguineus*, commonly referred to as the “brown dog tick,” is the most widespread tick species in the world.² Although they feed primarily on dogs, *R. linnaei* may also infect humans, causing risk of transmission of pathogens that can lead to human diseases such as Rocky Mountain Spotted Fever (*Rickettsia rickettsii*), Ehrlichiosis (*Ehrlichia chaffeensis*), and Anaplasmosis (*Anaplasma phagocytophilum*).³

Central America contains varied ecological settings and socioeconomic conditions rendering it vulnerable to vector-borne diseases. Competition over land cover for natural resources and human settlements has resulted in deforestation in many

Central American countries, including Belize.⁴ This affects vegetation and animals that live in the changing environment, potentially influencing tick species’ distribution and presence. Contact of ticks with humans depends mainly on the specific characteristics of the environment that each tick species requires.⁵

Domestic dogs in Belize are commonly used to protect agricultural crops from predators and for hunting.⁶ Past studies have shown that dogs could be used as sampled animals for tick surveillance in Belize.⁷ Additionally, previous studies have found that a presence of infected ticks suggests an increased risk of exposure to rickettsioses in humans and animals in Belize.⁸ As land cover changes due to deforestation and associated animal populations occur, interactions between dogs and *R. linnaei* may also shift, resulting in an increased or decreased risk of tick-borne diseases to resident communities. The objective of this study was to quantify deforestation in two communities in Belize and to assess the relationship between the presence of adult *R. linnaei* and land cover change.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Tick sampling was performed in January 2020 at randomly selected houses within San Lazaro and Indian Church communities of Orange Walk District, Belize, Central America (Figure 1).

Census data from the 2010 National Survey provided by the Statistical Institute of Belize was used to determine the number

1 Mächtinger, E.; Poh, K.; Pesapane, R.; Tufts, D. An integrative framework for tick management: the need to connect wildlife science, One Health, and interdisciplinary perspectives. *Current Opinion in Insect Science* 61: 2214 - 5745

2 Dantas-Torres, F. 2008. The brown dog tick, *Rhipicephalus sanguineus*: from taxonomy to control. *Veterinary Parasitology* 152: 173-185.

3 Doyle C.; Beach T.; Luzzadder-Beach S. 2021. Tropical forest and wetland losses and the role of protected areas in northwestern Belize, revealed from landsat and machine learning. *Remote Sensing* 13:379.

4 Parola, P.; Socolovschi, C.; Jeanjean, L.; Bitam, I.; Fournier, P.; Sotto, A.; Labauge, P.; Raoult, D. 2008. Warmer weather linked to tick attack and emergence of severe rickettsioses. *Neglected Tropical Diseases*.

5 Ortiz, D. I.; Piche-Ovares, M.; Romero-Vega, L. M.; Wagman, J.; Troyo, A. 2022. The impact of deforestation, urbanization, and changing land use patterns on the ecology of mosquito and tick-borne diseases in central America. *Insects* 13: 20.

6 Casino, M. M. Personal Communication, October 2023.

7 Pilsomboon Nelson S, Bourke BP, Badr R, Tarpey J, Caicedo-Quiroga L, Leiva D, Pott M, Cruz A, Chao CC, Achee NL, Grieco JP. 2022. Ticks (Acari: Ixodidae) and Associated Pathogens Collected From Domestic Animals and Vegetation in Stann Creek District, Southeastern Belize, Central America. *Journal of Medical Entomology*. Sep 1;59(5):1749-55

8 Pilsomboon S, Hoel DE, Murphy JR, Linton YM, Motoki M, Robbins RG, Bautista K, Briceño I, Achee NL, Grieco JP, Ching WM. 2017. Molecular detection and identification of Rickettsia species in ticks (Acari: Ixodidae) collected from Belize, Central America. *Journal of Medical Entomology*, Nov 7;54(6):1718-26.

of households in both San Lazaro and Indian Church, and 10% of houses in each community were sampled to be surveyed. This number was generated by a random point simulation in Quantum GIS (QGIS 3.10.10 'A Coruña') to randomly select which homes would be a part of the study by overlaying a satellite image of each community and picking the homes that the points touched. Homeowners of the sampled houses were informed of the study objectives and guided the field team on which dogs could be inspected for ticks. De-identified (blurred) GPS coordinates of sampled households were recorded using longitude and latitude units of approximately 18.04 N and -88.66 W for San Lazaro and 17.75 N and -88.65 W for Indian Church for use in layering onto satellite images of each community. Ticks were collected from domestic dogs by trained staff of the Belize Vector and Ecology Center (BVEC). Ticks from each dog were removed with fine-tipped forceps and placed into individual vials containing 5 mL of isopropyl alcohol labeled by date and location. The ticks were then transported to the BVEC laboratory for morphological species identification and further processing.

Ticks were shipped to the University of Notre Dame for Total Nucleic Acid (TNA) extraction and molecular species identification using Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) Sequencing methodology (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Processing and Sequencing Steps. The chart on the left lists the steps for tick processing, and the chart on the right shows the steps for tick testing and identification.

Briefly, ticks were processed individually for TNA extraction.⁹ Tick samples were homogenized in a dry ice-chilled Bullet Blender (Next Advances, USA) using beads of various sizes. TNA from ground samples was extracted using the IndiMag Pathogen Kit (Indical Bioscience GmbH, Germany) and KingFisher Flex (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). After TNA extraction, DNA and RNA concentrations were measured using a Qubit 4.0 fluorometer (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA). After

this was completed, tick testing was undertaken using GridION (Oxford Nanopore Technologies) sequencer in order to confirm species identification according to the published REDI-NET Standard Operating Procedures (SOP).¹⁰ A maximum of 150 ng of gDNA sample was subjected to library preparation and sequencing using the ONT rapid barcoding kit (SQK-RBK110.96, ONT, UK). A total of 24-48 individually barcoded samples were pooled, loaded on a R9.4.1 flow cell (ONT, UK), and run for 48 hours on a GridION equipment (ONT, UK). Resulting sequences were aligned against the non-redundant (nr) protein database by DIAMOND and inspected with the MEGAN6 program. Extracted reads were then compared to BLAST+ nucleotide alignment for species confirmation.¹¹

Quantification of *R. linnaei* was conducted using sequence outputs by assigning a binary code to each dog sample indicating one of two groups: '0' representing either no tick collected or a tick species identified as other than *R. linnaei*; and '1' representing at least one *R. linnaei* tick confirmed as identified in the sample.

Deforestation was estimated using land cover as an indicator based on a 200-square-foot area surrounding the center of each San Lazaro and Indian Church home. Satellite images (Google Earth Pro) generated in January 2017 were compared to images from March 2022. A triplet code was assigned to land cover type using visual observation of 4x4 grids overlaid to GPS locations of each sampled house: forest = '0'; bare ground = '1'; and buildings = '2' (Fig. 3A & B). Grids were manually color-coded red or green to differentiate forested land cover from other land cover types (Fig. 4A & B).

Figure 3: Land cover grids from 2017 (A) and 2022 (B) in San Lazaro. Google Earth Pro satellite imagery was used to capture this historical land data. The star in each image represents the reference point for the center of the 200 square foot area. Over this span of time, there was an 80% decrease in forest (0), 100% decrease in bare land (1), and 50% increase in built land (2).

⁹ REDI-NET Consortium 2024. T-2 TICK PROCESSING. Protocols.io <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.36wgqjx75vk5/v1>

10 REDI-NET Consortium 2024. T-2 TICK PROCESSING. Protocols.io <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.36wgqjx75vk5/v1>

¹¹ REDI-NET Consortium 2024. T-4 TICK TESTING. Protocols.io <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kxygx3ozzg8j/v1>

RESULTS

A total of 36 dogs from 31 houses in San Lazaro and 19 dogs from 11 houses in Indian Church were sampled. From all collections, a total of 421 ticks were collected, processed, and sequenced for species identification. Among these, 3 species were dominantly found. Three hundred and sixty-three tick samples were identified as *R. linnaei* (86.2%); 39 as *Rhipicephalus spp.* (9.3%), and 6 as *Rhipicephalus microplus* (1.4%). *R. linnaei* represented 86.8% (249/287) of all ticks captured from sampled dogs in San Lazaro and 85.1% (114/134) in Indian Church. Furthermore, 91.5% of sampled houses in San Lazaro contained a dog with at least one *R. linnaei*, whereas 77.2% of sampled houses in Indian Church contained a dog with at least one *R. linnaei*.

The average rate of deforestation (using percentage of bare ground as a proxy indicator) was estimated at 31.2% in San Lazaro and 4.6% in Indian Church over the assessed 5-year period (2017-2022). In addition, there was a 24.2% increase of land cover categorized as buildings in San Lazaro, with only a 10.6% increase of buildings in Indian Church.

DISCUSSION

The objective of this study was to assess the relationship between the presence of *R. linnaei* and land cover change in the communities of San Lazaro and Indian Church, northern Belize, Central America. A greater presence of *R. linnaei* was associated with increased deforestation, as seen in San Lazaro. On the other hand, lower presence rates of *R. linnaei* were associated with lower levels of land cover change and lower levels of deforestation, as seen in Indian Church. These results support the hypothesis that increased land cover changes in Belize are associated with increased presence of the brown dog tick. Although there have not been other studies to this day related to deforestation and tick-borne pathogens in Belize, studies conducted in Central America have found a link between

deforestation and increased malaria transmission.¹² Moreover, previous studies have shown that increased tick presence can lead to increased transmission rates of harmful vector-borne diseases to humans.¹³ Therefore, this associated link between deforestation and increased tick presence can impact the health of the overall population.

Some limitations include a small number of houses sampled in only two villages, as well as a small set of years in which land cover change was analyzed, which could lead to bias. Ticks were collected in 2020 and not across a multiyear span, limiting our ability to investigate any evolution in the density of *R. linnaei* at the studied villages. Census data could not be found over the investigated time periods of 2017 to 2022, as only census data from 2010 and 2020 are available.

This study can be expanded upon in order to further support the proposed relationship between land cover change and risks for exposure to vector-borne diseases. Future studies might analyze disease transmission in the selected village sites by looking at the presence of pathogens in the tick samples. Additionally, expansion of data collection to a broader time span may provide further context as to how these results may have changed over time. In the future, more sites should be selected and observed in order to further investigate the way in which land cover change can increase the risk of exposure to tick-borne pathogens, and future studies should integrate population-level census data as well. Regardless of these limitations and challenges, the results of this study can still contribute to increasing knowledge on the risk of tick-borne diseases.

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12 Ortiz, D. I.; Piche-Ovares, M.; Romero-Vega; L. M.; Wagman, J.; Troyo, A. 2022.
13 Polsomboon S, Hoel DF, Murphy JR, Linton YM, Motoki M, Robbins RG, Bautista K, Briceño I, Achee NL, Grieco JB, Ching WM. 2017.

support, the study would not have been successful.

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Developing 3D tumor models for neuroendocrine prostate cancer to facilitate disease characterization and enhance sustainability in the laboratory

by Ella Foster '24

ABSTRACT

Culturing tumor cells in three dimensions has been gaining popularity in the laboratory due to the ability to more accurately characterize the *in vivo* tumor microenvironment during preclinical studies. Prostate cancer is the second most common cancer in men, and although often curable, prostate adenocarcinomas can develop into neuroendocrine prostate cancer (NEPC), a lethal and aggressive subset of prostate cancer that is resistant to conventional drug treatments. Three-dimensional models for studying the neuroendocrine transition in prostate cancer are limited, and have mainly been carried out in Matrigel, which is an animal-derived scaffold that raises issues regarding sustainability and reproducibility. Synthetic hydrogels are becoming increasingly popular due to their ability to effectively mimic the ECM while reducing animal life requirements and improving batch-to-batch consistency. The efficacy of GrowDex was determined for two prostate cancer cell lines by measuring spheroid-forming efficiency and cell viability in comparison to the gold standard animal-derived matrices, GelTrex and Matrigel. Although spheroid-forming efficiency was limited in GrowDex for NEPC cell line LASCPC-01, comparable efficacy to Matrigel and GelTrex was found for the adenocarcinoma prostate cancer cell line, LNCaP. Additionally, gene expression analysis by RT-qPCR in LNCaPs cultured in GrowDex, Matrigel, and GelTrex suggested that all three affect the expression of NEPC markers similarly in LNCaPs by causing general upregulation relative to 2D culture. Previous studies have shown that 3D culture induces greater chemotherapy resistance in LNCaPs compared to 2D culture, and the observed upregulation of NEPC markers seen in this study suggests that 3D culture may serve as a model for another type of treatment resistance through the neuroendocrine transition.

INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensional culture of cancer cells is gaining popularity in the laboratory due to the ability to more accurately model tumor structure and physiology compared with a two-dimensional plate. Although 2D culture of tumor cells allows for fast proliferation, high reproducibility, and high-throughput screening, it is unable to fully encapsulate the cell-cell interactions, morphology, and gene expression of *in vivo* tumor cells that exist in three-dimensional space.¹ Tumor cells tend to adhere to the bottom of the plate when grown in 2D culture, which causes cellular arrangement to differ between 2D culture and tumors *in vivo*. Differences in structure can cause the cultured cells to exhibit different properties in viability and gene expression, potentially reducing the ability to translate the

results of *in vitro* experiments to *in vivo* studies. For example, gene expression differs between cells that exist in different environments, as conserving cell-cell interactions in a 3D structure requires proteins that are not expressed by cells cultured in 2D.² Additionally, 3D clusters of cells better mimic access to resources than 2D cultures, as there is a gradient of resource availability in a cluster, while adherent cells in 2D culture have equal access to resources in the culture medium.³

Culturing cancer cells in a 3D scaffold offers to enable both high-throughput screening and representative modeling of tumors. The polymeric structure of these scaffolds mimics the extracellular matrix (ECM) and can thereby recapitulate the *in vivo* interactions between cells and the ECM.⁴ Tumor invasion of tissues has been shown to depend on the rigidity of the surrounding ECM, so using a polymeric scaffold to model the stiffness of the tumor microenvironment will provide more insight into tumor growth properties.⁵ By culturing cancer cells in a 3D scaffold, more accurate predictions about cellular response to treatment may be made *in vitro* without requiring any animal tissue. This type of model is thereby well-suited for high-throughput screening, and assays performed with 3D models may be more biologically relevant than 2D due to their biomimetic structure.

Organoid model development has become increasingly prevalent in prostate cancer research. A variety of different organoid models have been developed recently, and their relevance has been demonstrated by the differential properties observed in comparison to their 2D counterparts. For example, Edmonson, *et al.* developed an organoid model for prostate cancer using LNCaP epithelial cells cultured in Matrigel (a scaffold containing sheets of ECM isolated from a mouse tumor).⁶ This organoid model showed significantly lower sensitivity to the chemotherapy drug Docetaxel compared to 2D-cultured LNCaPs, demonstrating the variability between culture conditions in modeling therapeutic responses. In addition, Van Deusen, *et al.* developed a neuroendocrine prostate cancer (NEPC) organoid by culturing epithelial NCI-H660 cells in the 18 QGel 3D Matrix.⁷ Compared to 2D culture, a higher dose of AD80 (a RET pathway inhibitor) was required to cause 50% cell death in 3D culture. These studies demonstrate that developing 3D models for different subsets of prostate cancer is both possible and worthwhile, as cell behavior varies across models.

However, as 3D culture grows, so do the environmental concerns about the sustainability of its scaffolds. The gold standard for 3D culture scaffolds is Matrigel, which is an animal-derived matrix obtained from mouse sarcomas.⁸ Although this material effectively mimics the ECM and promotes cellular proliferation, its production has a high mouse life requirement, which ideally would be minimized for *in vitro* culturing techniques.⁸ The vast number of vertebrate animals bred in laboratories is not a frequently discussed statistic because laboratories are not required to report these numbers. However, animal usage makes substantial contributions to waste production, groundwater runoff, and fossil fuel emission from carcass incinera-

tion.⁹ Although *in vivo* animal experiments are invaluable for predicting how humans will respond to different therapies, the requirement for animal lives should be reduced wherever possible when developing *in vitro* models. Synthetic and plant-based scaffolds are emerging as potential sustainable alternatives to animal-derived scaffolds, and are being investigated for their ability to promote cellular proliferation and differentiation without requiring animal lives. One such plant-based scaffold is GrowDex, which is a birch tree-derived hydrogel that is composed of nanofibrillated cellulose polymers.¹⁰ Studies comparing 3D culture success between GrowDex and Matrigel have shown promising results so far, and this study aims to expand this effort to the study of a rare subset of prostate cancer with limited available 3D culture protocols.¹¹

Neuroendocrine prostate cancer (NEPC) is an aggressive, treatment-resistant type of prostate cancer that evolves as prostate cancer adenocarcinomas become resistant to traditional treatments for prostate cancer. Prostate adenocarcinomas consist of luminal epithelial cells that are dependent on androgen receptor (AR) signaling. Androgen receptor inhibitors (ARis) are thereby promising therapeutic compounds, although their long-term efficacy is believed to be limited by the ability of luminal cells to differentiate into androgen-independent, neuroendocrine phenotypes. This proposed mechanism is called lineage plasticity, in which loss of tumor suppressor genes RB1, TP53, and PTEN allows cells to re-differentiate in response to changes in their environment, including drug exposure.¹² Previous studies have shown that LNCaP adenocarcinoma cells cultured in 3D are more resistant to chemotherapeutic compounds like Docetaxel, but there has been little investigation into the effects of 3D culture on adenocarcinoma resistance to ARi treatment and the neuroendocrine transition. I hypothesize that because the morphology of LNCaPs cultured in 3D is more similar to that of neuroendocrine prostate cancer cell lines, there may be an upregulation in NEPC gene markers compared to LNCaPs cultured in 2D conditions. If the transition to 3D culture can be used to induce the lineage plasticity transition from luminal to neuroendocrine prostate cancer, these models may help to identify treatments that can reverse or prevent this process.

The goals of this study are two-pronged. First, to expand the landscape of 3D model protocols available for this rare subset of prostate cancer, with a focus on sustainable alternatives to the commonly used animal-derived products. Second, to determine whether 3D culture of adenocarcinoma cell lines can be used to model the neuroendocrine transition, and gain insight into this mechanism of treatment resistance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cell Lines and Culture Media: Two human prostate cancer cell lines, LNCaP and LASCPC-01, were purchased from American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) for culture in 2D and 3D. LNCaP is a loosely adherent epithelial cell line in 2D culture that was isolated from the adenocarcinoma of a 50 year old man, and is cultured in RPMI-1640 with 10% fetal

bovine serum and 1% penicillin-streptomycin. LASCPC-01 is a floating, aggregate-forming cell line that was isolated from the prostate of a 75-80 year old man with prostate cancer. This cell line is a model for NEPC due to its expression of N-Myc, which is a known driver for NEPC. LASCPC-01 is cultured in HITES medium (RPMI 1640 with 5 µg/mL insulin, 10 µg/mL transferrin, 30 nM sodium selenite, 10 nM hydrocortisone, 10 nM β-estradiol, and 10 mM HEPES).

3D Culture Materials: Corning® Matrigel® Growth Factor Reduced (GFR) Basement Membrane Matrix, *LDEV-Free, was purchased from Corning® and diluted 1:2 with cell medium to give a protein concentration of ~5 mg/ml. Gibco™ Geltrex™ LDEV-Free Reduced Growth Factor Basement Membrane Matrix was ordered from Fisher Scientific, and diluted 1:2 with cell medium to give a protein concentration of ~5 mg/ml. GrowDex® was purchased from Revvity Health Sciences Inc.

3D Culture Protocols:

Matrigel and Geltrex: Matrigel and Geltrex are derived from the same basement membrane matrix (Engelbreth-Holm-Swarm tumor) and have similar protein concentrations. As a result, the same protocol was used for 3D culture preparation in each matrix per Corning® guidelines.¹³ Each matrix stock was thawed overnight prior to seeding, and then diluted 1:2 with the medium appropriate for the cell line to be seeded. All Matrigel and Geltrex solutions were kept ice cold throughout the procedure to prevent premature gel formation. In a 48-well plate, each well was coated evenly with 100 µL of Matrigel or Geltrex and incubated for 30 minutes at 37°C to allow for gel formation. A 100 µL mixture of matrix and cells (90 µL of Matrigel/Geltrex with 60,000 cells collected in 10 µL of medium) was dispensed on top of the solidified base layer, and incubated at 37°C for 45 minutes. After formation of the second layer, 100 µL of medium was added gently to the top. The top layer of medium was changed every 2 days, and 3D cultures were dissociated on Day 5 for downstream analysis.

GrowDex: Prepared per UPM Biomedicals guidelines.¹⁴ A 150 µL mixture of GrowDex and cells (75 µL of GrowDex with 60,000 cells collected in 25 µL of medium) was seeded into each well of a 48-well plate, and 150 µL of medium was added on top. The top layer of medium was changed every 2 days, and 3D cultures were dissociated on Day 5 for downstream analysis.

Cell Imaging: 2D and 3D cultures were imaged regularly to monitor cell morphology and proliferation. All images were taken with a Leica confocal microscope.

Release of Cells from 3D Culture:

Matrigel and GelTrex: Dispase solution (5 U/mL) was diluted 1:5 in Hanks' Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS), and 150 μ L was added to each well of the 48-well plate. After incubating the plate for 1 hour, the contents of each well were collected and centrifuged (300g for 5 minutes at 4°C). The cell pellet was washed in Dulbecco's Phosphate Buffered Saline (D-PBS) and centrifuged (300g for 5 minutes at 4°C). The resulting cell pellet was then resuspended in the appropriate medium for downstream analysis.

GrowDex: GrowDex cultures were dissociated per UPM Biomedical Instructions.¹⁵ 450 μ g of GrowDase® (purchased from Revvity Health Sciences Inc.) was added per 1 mg of cellulose (33.75 μ L of GrowDase per well in a 48-well plate). Cell medium was added to GrowDase to give a total volume equal to the contents of the well (116.25 μ L to give a total of 150 μ L). The plate was incubated at 37°C for at least 8 hours, and then collected and centrifuged (300g for 5 minutes at 4°C). The cell pellet was washed with D-PBS as described above and resuspended in appropriate medium for downstream analysis.

2D Culture: LNCaP - After aspirating cell medium, 1 mL of Trypsin was added to a 10-cm cell culture dish and the plate was incubated at 37°C for 2 minutes. 2 mL of cell medium were then added to neutralize the Trypsin, and the contents were centrifuged (300g for 5 minutes at 4°C). The cell pellet was washed with D-PBS as described above and resuspended in appropriate medium for downstream analysis.

LASCPC-01 - The cell-containing medium was collected and centrifuged (300g for 5 minutes at 4°C). The cell pellet was washed with D-PBS as described above and resuspended in appropriate medium for downstream analysis.

Cell Count and Viability: 10 μ L of cell solution was diluted 1:2 with 10 μ L of Trypan blue dye and dispersed into a disposable Countess chamber slide. The slide was inserted into a Countess Automated Cell Counter, and cell count and viability were recorded from the machine readout.

RT-qPCR: RNA extraction was performed on the cells collected from 2D and 3D cultures with the BioBasic RNA Extraction Kit per instructions.¹⁶ cDNA synthesis was performed with the All-In-One 5X RT MasterMix per Applied Biological Materials (ABM) instructions. RT-qPCR was carried out by running a qPCR protocol on the BioRad qPCR system. The expression levels of various prostate cancer markers (AR, PSA, ENO2, EZH2, ASCL1, SYP, and CHGA) were tested in each culture condition relative to the housekeeping gene, GAPDH, and normalized to expression levels in 2D culture.

RESULTS

I. Spheroid-forming capacity of LNCaP and LASCPC-01 in 2D and 3D culture conditions

Figure 1: Brightfield LNCaP images taken with 10X objective lens taken on Day 5 after seeding 3D cultures. A) LNCaPs cultured in 2D are adherent and exhibit epithelial morphology. B) Robust spheroid formation was observed for LNCaPs cultured in Matrigel GFR. C) Spheroid formation in Standard Matrigel occurred to a similar extent Matrigel GFR, although the spheroids tended to be smaller. D) Spheroid formation in GelTrex was very comparable to Standard Matrigel. E) While large spheroids formed in GrowDex similarly to the other 3D cultures, the spheroids tended to be more sparse.

Spheroid formation was observed in LNCaPs seeded in each 3D culture condition tested (Matrigel GFR, Matrigel Std., GelTrex, and GrowDex). **Fig. 1** shows images taken of LNCaPs on Day 5 after seeding in each 3D culture condition and 2D culture. The epithelial, spindle-like morphology of LNCaPs cultured in 2D can be seen in Fig. 1A, in contrast to the densely aggregated spheroids formed in 3D culture. The most robust spheroid formation was observed in Matrigel GFR, as these cultures had the largest spheroid sizes and densities (Fig. 1B). Similar densities of spheroids were observed in Matrigel Std. and GelTrex, although spheroid diameters tended to be smaller than in Matrigel GFR (Fig. 1C, 1D). In GrowDex, lower densities of spheroids were observed than the animal-derived matrices, but the spheroids that did form were of comparable size (Fig. 1E). LNCaPs appear to be well-suited for different forms of 3D culture, including GrowDex. Because GrowDex lacks the growth factors present in animal-derived matrices, spheroid growth is expected to be slower in this culture condition. However, its viability as a method for modeling *in vivo* tumor conditions is supported by the observed formation of distinct spheroids, and the number of cells isolated on Day 5 proved to be sufficient for downstream analysis, as will be discussed in the following sections.

Figure 2: Brightfield LASCPC-01 images taken with 10X objective lens taken on Day 5 after seeding 3D cultures.

A) LASCPC-01 cultured in 2D are floating and aggregate-forming. B) Dense cluster formation was observed for LASCPC-01 cultured in Standard Matrigel. D) Very little cluster formation and cell growth were observed for GelTrex cultures. E) LASCPC-01 cultured in GrowDex appeared very similar to the original 2D culture and lacked signs of spheroid formation.

LASCPC-01 cells were cultured in the same conditions as LNCaP and demonstrated more variable responses to the 3D cultures tested (Figure 2). In 2D, LASCPC-01 is a rapidly growing cell line that forms floating aggregates and exhibits small cell carcinoma morphology (Fig. 2A).¹⁷ In contrast to the spindle-like, adherent epithelial appearance of LNCaPs, LASCPC-01 cells are small and round with nuclei that are difficult to visualize.¹⁸ Spheroid formation was only observed to be effective in Matrigel GFR and Matrigel Std., with Matrigel Std. forming the most robust spheroids (Fig. 2B, 2C). Despite multiple attempts to culture LASCPC-01 in GelTrex, little success was observed across sets of triplicates to promote spheroid formation in this material (Fig. 2D). Additionally, LASCPC-01 cells consistently failed to form clusters in GrowDex (Fig. 2E). The cells grew very similarly to cells grown in 2D culture, with cell aggregates but no signs of spheroid formation.

Figure 3: Effect of varying GrowDex percent concentration (0.25% and 0.5%) on spheroid formation of LASCPC-01 and LNCaP. Top: Inappreciable amounts of spheroid formation were observed for LASCPC-01 regardless of the percent concentration used. Bottom: For LNCaP, spheroid formation occurred to a comparable level in each concentration of GrowDex tested.

Two GrowDex concentrations were tested (0.25% and 0.5%) to see if different levels of scaffold rigidity would promote cell growth (Figure 3). It was found that changing the concentration of GrowDex did not change the spheroid forming efficiency of either LNCaP or LASCPC-01, as LNCaP formed robust spheroids at both concentrations, while LASCPC-01 did not do so in either.

II. Cell count and viability of LNCaP and LASCPC-01 in each type of 3D culture

On Day 5, each 3D culture condition was dissociated by the protocols described in the Methods section, and the isolated cells were analyzed for cell count and percent viability (Figure 4). The percentages of viable cells isolated were high (average > 75%) in each type of 3D culture condition, suggesting that Matrigel GFR, GelTrex, and GrowDex each create a hospitable environment for both LASCPC-01 and LNCaP (Fig. 3A, 3B).

Figure 4: Cell viabilities and counts for LNCaP and LASCPC-01 on Day 5 in each 3D culture condition. A and B) Triplicate measurements of cell viability suggest that for both LNCaP and LASCPC-01, cell viability levels were comparable across each culture condition. C and D) LASCPC-01 and LNCaP cell counts were significantly higher for GrowDex than Matrigel GFR and GelTrex.

The cell counts determined after matrix dissociation were more variable, however. For both LASCPC-01 and LNCaP, significantly more cells were isolated from GrowDex than Matrigel GFR and GelTrex. This result was unexpected based on the images shown in **Fig. 1** and **Fig. 2**, as the spheroid density generally appeared to be much higher in the animal-derived matrices. However, the elevated cell counts were likely due to the method for releasing cells from GrowDex being more efficient than the animal-derived matrices. GrowDase is a commercially available enzyme that degrades the cellulose polymer comprising GrowDex, and appears to be a more effective dissociation method than the degradation of Matrigel and GelTrex with dispase and HBSS (see Methods section). Although the number of cells harvested in all conditions was sufficient for RNA extraction, the ability to harvest significantly more cells from GrowDex suggests a merit of this material and the need to optimize methods of dissociation for the animal-derived matrices.

III. Gene expression of LNCaP cultured in 3D vs. 2D culture

As another metric for comparison between the different 3D culture conditions, expression of common markers for prostate cancer was measured relative to 2D culture controls using RT-qPCR (**Fig. 5**). Two of the markers tested in LNCaP were PSA and AR, both of which are overexpressed in prostate cancer adenocarcinomas, the most common form of prostate cancer that is responsive to ARi treatment. The other three markers tested, ENO2, ASCL1, and SYP, are overexpressed in NEPC, which is the more aggressive and treatment-resistant form of prostate cancer.

Figure 5: Expression of prostate cancer gene markers in LNCaPs that are cultured in 3D vs. 2D. Across each type of 3D matrix tested (Matrigel GFR, GelTrex, and GrowDex), a general trend of NEPC marker overexpression and adenocarcinoma marker underexpression was observed. The fold change in expression was calculated using the delta-delta Ct method for quantitative PCR.

Based on preliminary analysis of NEPC marker expression in each 3D matrix, it was found that the general trends of upregulation and downregulation in LNCaPs were conserved

across all three conditions. Upregulation of NEPC markers in 3D culture relative to 2D was observed, suggesting that the transition to a 3D environment may push LNCaPs toward a neuroendocrine phenotype. Moreover, the relative fold changes in AR and PSA expression were significantly lower than the NEPC markers, reinforcing the possibility of a phenotypic shift. ASCL1, a transcription factor that was found to be highly upregulated in each 3D culture condition, is known to promote lineage plasticity through epigenetic reprogramming mechanisms, suggesting a potential mechanism for the development of NEPC markers and disappearance adenocarcinoma markers after culturing in 3D. If 3D culture does emulate this phenotypic transition, identifying the elements involved may assist in the development of targeted treatments preventing the transition to more aggressive forms of prostate cancer in patients.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results regarding cell viability, spheroid formation, and gene expression, GrowDex appears to be a suitable alternative to the animal-derived matrices for LNCaP. While LNCaP spheroids form more sparsely in GrowDex, there are a variety of benefits to this material beyond including its easily tunable composition and highly effective method of degradation. Being able to collect the majority of the cells embedded within the gel allows for downstream analyses that are more representative of cells in culture. Additionally, the preparation process for GrowDex is much faster and simpler than the animal-derived matrices, as there is no requirement for all reagents to remain ice cold throughout or series of coating and gel solidification stages. One drawback of the material is that the cellulose polymer creates background noise in images that can make it more difficult to identify spheroids. Overall, however, GrowDex is a user-friendly scaffolding material that modulated the appearance, viability, and gene expression of LNCaPs comparably to Matrigel GFR and GelTrex, suggesting its potential for use as a more sustainable alternative for 3D culture for this cell line.

The LASCPC-01 cell line, however, was not successfully cultured in GrowDex, as there was no observable spheroid formation. This protocol requires further optimization, and one potential modification for the future would be to increase the percent concentration of GrowDex used to above 0.5%. A lower concentration of GrowDex (0.25%) was chosen for comparison with the baseline 0.5% based on the growth-enhancing effects of decreasing percent concentration of GrowDex on growth of HepG2 cells observed by Feodoroff, *et al.* (2023).¹⁹ However, HepG2 cells are epithelial in morphology and thereby may respond differently to GrowDex than the small cell phenotype of LASCPC-01. Increasing instead of decreasing the concentration of GrowDex may help to promote spheroid formation of LASCPC-01 in this material. Additionally, RGD peptides are responsible for cell adhesion to the extracellular matrix, and addition of these peptides has been shown to enhance the growth of cell lines in GrowDex that were previously not able to be cultured in this scaffold.²⁰ This cell line has not previously been cultured in GrowDex, and further optimiza-

tion is required to create a viable alternative to the animal-derived matrices.

Moreover, analysis of expression of prostate cancer markers in LNCaPs cultured in 3D provided two primary pieces of insight. First, the general trends of upregulation and downregulation of NEPC markers were conserved across all three matrices, suggesting that the 3D environment causes predictable changes in gene expression. It is important to note, however, that despite conservation of trends, the three matrices tested differentially affected the degree to which the expression of these markers is altered, suggesting the importance of comparing these expression levels to *in vivo* tumor samples in the future to determine which model is most representative. The second piece of insight obtained from marker expression analysis is that LNCaPs cultured in 3D tend to undergo increased expression of NEPC markers and decreased expression of adenocarcinoma markers relative to 2D culture. This finding raises the possibility of a neuroendocrine transition occurring during growth in 3D culture, and identifying the elements of the 3D environment that cause this transition may provide insight into the development of NEPC from adenocarcinomas in patients. My next step in studying this relationship is validation by Western blot to determine whether the patterns observed in mRNA expression are reflected by protein production. Additionally, I plan to test whether LNCaPs cultured in 3D respond differently to treatment with targeted therapies when compared with 2D controls. If 3D culture does enhance the expression of genes related to lineage plasticity like ASCL1, these cells may exhibit heightened resistance to targeted therapies due to the ability to switch phenotypes. By optimizing 3D culture protocols and analyzing gene expression, I aim to facilitate treatment development for NEPC by expanding the landscape of 3D models available and gaining deeper insight into the neuroendocrine transition.

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Bilingualism and Cognition in the Sacramento Area Latino Study on Aging (SALSA)

by Brooke Friedman^{1,2,4}

ABSTRACT

Aging is associated with cognitive decline. While there is some cognitive decline that occurs in healthy aging (Sánchez-Izquierdo & Fernández-Ballesteros, 2021), other disorders such as Alzheimer's and other dementias show a more severe decline in memory (Boyle et al., 2006; Celsis, 2000). Thus, is it necessary to investigate factors which may ameliorate cognitive decline in older adults. Bilingualism is one factor mentioned in the literature which may protect against cognitive decline and delay its onset (Alladi et al., 2013; Bialystok et al., 2007; Padilla et al., 2016); however, due to conflicting evidence, more research is needed to better understand this phenomenon (Chertkow et al., 2010; Zahodne et al., 2014). Here, we use the Sacramento Area Latino Study on Aging (SALSA) dataset to investigate the protective role of bilingualism on cognitive decline in a longitudinal sample of older bilingual Latinx adults in the Sacramento Area.

DOES BILINGUALISM PROTECT AGAINST COGNITIVE DECLINE

Bilingualism refers to dual-language acquisition, where an individual is able to proficiently communicate in both languages. In order to effectively switch between languages, it is theorized that bilingualism enhances a component of executive functioning known as response inhibition, where bilinguals are required to suppress one language during conversations with monolinguals (Bialystok et al., 2004; Green, 1998). This effect of bilingualism is dependent on the level of proficiency in the second language (L2), which is affected by length of immersion and frequency of L2 use (Jiang et al., 2009). Increased bilingualism may preserve intrinsic functional network organization in brain networks associated with attentional control and inhibition such as the default mode network (Stevens et al., 2023), which may allow the brain to cope with more neurodegeneration for a longer period of time without showing symptoms of cognitive decline (Perani et al., 2017).

Current research has conflicting findings regarding if bilingualism indeed protects against cognitive decline. Bilingualism has been shown to delay the onset of dementia between 4 - 4.5 years (Alladi et al., 2013; Bialystok et al., 2007; Craik et al., 2010), and higher second language (L2) acculturation has been shown to improve cognitive scores on neuropsychological tests among older Hispanics (Alam et al., 2022). A meta-analysis by Anderson and colleagues (2020) found a stronger protective effect for delaying the onset of cognitive decline, and a weaker protective effect for preventing its occurrence altogether (Anderson et al., 2020). However, conflicting findings have also been reported (for a review, see Van den Noort et al., 2019). In an analysis of the Australian Longitudinal Study of Ageing,

bilingualism did not significantly protect against cognitive decline (Mukadam et al., 2018). Other research suggests no effect of bilingualism on cognitive decline or dementia risk/onset beyond baseline (Torres et al., 2022; Zahodne et al., 2014). Thus, it is necessary to continue pursuing research in this area to better understand the influence of bilingualism in cognition.

THE SACRAMENTO AREA LATINO STUDY ON AGING (SALSA)

To better understand this discrepancy in findings between bilingualism and cognitive decline, two studies have used the Sacramento Area Latino Study on Aging (SALSA) database. Despite using the same database, the studies yielded different results. Padilla and colleagues (2016) found that bilingualism is associated with higher cognitive scores on the Modified Mini-Mental State Exam (3MS) at baseline. However, Lawton and colleagues (2015) found no significant difference between the mean age of diagnosis between the bilingual and monolingual groups, suggesting that bilingualism does not delay the onset of dementia. Thus, more research is necessary in this area.

THE PRESENT STUDY

The present study will use the SALSA dataset to investigate the relationship between bilingualism and cognitive decline in a longitudinal sample of older bilingual Latinx adults. Whereas Lawton and colleagues (2015) limited their analysis to adults diagnosed with Alzheimer's and dementia, this study uses a global measure of cognitive decline based on extensive neuropsychological test data. Furthermore, unlike Padilla and colleagues (2016), we examine the full sample (n = 764). Finally, we use a continuous composite measure of bilingualism. We hypothesize that higher levels of bilingualism will correspond to decreased cognitive decline.

METHODS

Participants: We performed a secondary analysis of the Sacramento Latino Study on Aging (SALSA) database, a study which recruited 1,789 participants from the Sacramento, California, metropolitan area and surrounding counties. Participants (51% immigrants, 89% from Mexico) were aged 60 or older and self-identified as Hispanic. Longitudinal data collection occurred from 1998 to 2008 every 12 to 15 months. We restricted our analyses to individuals who had complete data for demographic information and at least one time point of neuropsychological testing (n = 764). Informed consent was obtained from all participants and the University of California Davis Institutional Review Board approved study procedures.

Measures of Bilingualism: Bilingualism was assessed using a composite score of baseline information from the Acculturation Rating Scale for Mexican Americans-II (Cuellar et al., 1995). Participants were asked a series of questions pertaining to their frequency of interaction with the English language and Anglo individuals, and responses ranged from 0 (*Not at all*), 1 (*Not very often*), 2 (*Very often*), and 3 (*Almost always*). A sum score was calculated using a multiplier of 2 for the questions,

“Do you speak English?”, “Do you enjoy speaking English?”, “Do you enjoy TV, music, or movies in English?”, “Do you enjoy reading or writing in English?”, and “Is your thinking done in the English language?”, and a multiplier of 1 for the questions, “Do you associate with Anglos?”, “Were your childhood friends of Anglo origin?”, and “Are your friends now of Anglo origin?”. The maximum score was 40. Bilinguals were identified as having a score in the upper quartile range of 30-40 (n = 371), and monolinguals were identified as having a score in the lower quartile range of 0-10 (n = 393).

Measures of Cognition: Cognition was measured using the Spanish and English Neuropsychological Assessment Scales (SENAS) and the Modified Mini-Mental State Exam (3MS). SENAS was used to measure overall IQ (range 2.16 - 5.00), in addition to its six sub-tests (range 0 - 20): delayed recall, object naming, nonverbal semantic, verbal attention, verbal conceptualization, and pattern recognition. 3MS (range 0 - 100) produced an overall score and was used to screen global cognitive fluency across four domains: verbal memory/fluency, language/executive, orientation/visuoconstruction, and language/praxis (Rapp et al., 2003). Scores were calculated at baseline and longitudinally across five time points, with higher scores representing higher accuracy.

Statistical analyses: Bilingualism was treated as a categorical variable, dummy coded as 0 for monolingual and 1 for bilingual. Mixed effect models included participants as random effects (random intercepts). The models were analyzed using the “lme4”, “lmerTest”, and “broom.mixed” packages using maximum likelihood in R (version 4.2.2). We examined the effect of bilingualism on (1) baseline cognitive scores and (2) longitudinal cognitive scores. Covariates included age and a standardized socioeconomic score, created by summing each participant’s z-score for years of education and z-score for household income.

Two models were compared for the 3MS scores and for the SENAS scores. For each test score, the models included the interaction between language status (monolingual or bilingual) and the longitudinal scores as well as age as a mean-centered fixed effect, and participants as a random effect. The full model also included the standardized composite SES as an additional fixed effect. For the 3MS scores the likelihood-ratio test indicated that the full model provided a better fit for the data than the reduced model without the composite SES, $X^2(1) = 29.87$, $p < .001$. Likewise, the likelihood-ratio test for the SENAS scores indicated that the full model provided a better fit for the data than the reduced model without the composite SES, $X^2(1) = 31.31$, $p < .001$.

RESULTS

Direct Effect: There were six significant direct effects of bilingualism on cognition, such that bilinguals had higher baseline scores for the 3MS ($\beta = 5.43$, $p < .01$, 95% CI [2.07, 8.79]), object naming test ($\beta = 2.42$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [1.83, 3.01]), nonverbal semantic test ($\beta = 3.00$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [2.43, 3.58]), verbal attention test ($\beta = 1.32$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.63, 2.00]), verbal conceptualization test ($\beta = 2.34$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [1.70, 2.97]), and pattern recognition test ($\beta = 1.92$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [1.26, 2.58]). However, IQ score and delayed recall score did not show a significant main effect of bilingualism on cognition. All significant results are shown in Figure 1, where average scores for bilinguals are pink and monolinguals are blue. A higher score indicates better test performance, such that average scores for bilinguals on these tests were both descriptively and significantly higher than monolinguals.

Figure 1. Average baseline test scores among bilingual and monolingual groups. A ** denotes $p < .01$, and a *** denotes $p < .001$.

Interaction Effect: There were three significant interaction effects between time (i.e., longitudinal time point of data collection) and bilingual status on cognition. Specifically, the interaction was significant for the delayed recall test ($\beta = -.60$, $p < .01$, 95% CI [-1.03, -.16]), nonverbal semantic test ($\beta = -.42$, $p < .05$, 95% CI [-.84, -.01]), and pattern recognition test ($\beta = -.58$, $p < .05$, 95% CI [-1.07, -.10]). The 3MS assessment showed a marginally significant interaction ($\beta = -2.36$, $p = 0.068$, 95% CI [-4.90, .18]). However, these interactions were due to only the baseline scores being significantly higher for the bilinguals than the monolinguals but not the later time points.

DISCUSSION

The present study investigated the relationship between bilingualism and cognitive decline using the SALSA dataset, a cohort of older Latinx individuals who emigrated to the Sacramento Area. We created a comprehensive measure of bilingualism using the Acculturation Rating Scale for Mexican Americans-II to create a composite score, and subsequently chose the upper and lower 25% to determine bilinguals and monolinguals, respectively. There were six significant direct effects of bilingualism on cognition at baseline (3MS, object naming, nonverbal semantic, verbal attention, verbal

conceptualization, and pattern recognition tests) where bilinguals significantly outperformed monolinguals. There were also three significant interaction effects of time and bilingual status on cognition for the delayed recall, nonverbal semantic, and pattern recognition tests. However, this interaction was only attributed to the higher baseline scores but not later time points.

Our results confirm the findings of Padilla and colleagues (2016). In their work, they used the SALSA dataset to investigate the effect of bilingualism on cognition and measured bilingualism only through one question, “Do you speak English?”. Bilinguals were defined as those who responded “Not very often,” “Very often,” and “Almost always” which encompasses individuals who have weak proficiency in English. They found that there was a significant protective effect of bilingualism on baseline 3MS scores but not longitudinal 3MS scores. Our results confirm this finding, and further extend it to include five out of six SENAS tests using a significantly more descriptive and comprehensive bilingual measure (which assesses only those who have strong proficiency in English, i.e., the top 25% of bilinguals). Together, this study and ours suggest that there is a strong protective effect of bilingualism on cognitive decline in the SALSA dataset.

Another key study which investigated this topic using the SALSA dataset is Lawton and colleagues (2015), who did not find a significant effect of bilingualism on mean age of dementia diagnosis. Their study used a slightly more comprehensive assessment of bilingualism than Padilla and colleagues (“Do you speak English?” and “Do you speak Spanish?”), but did not use other questions from the Acculturation Rating Scale for Mexican Americans-II. Combining this with their relatively small sample size ($n = 81$), which may not have given enough power to detect an effect, it is possible that these factors yielded nonsignificance despite using the same SALSA dataset. This suggestion that their study is under-powered is supported by previous meta-analyses, which suggest that the link between bilingualism and age of onset of cognitive decline / other dementias is more reliably replicated than incidence or severity of cognitive decline (Anderson et al., 2020; Van den Noort et al., 2019).

Future research should continue to prioritize a comprehensive measure of bilingualism in order to discern precisely how bilingualism affects cognition (Luk & Bialystok, 2013). In time, this will hopefully shed light on the current conflicting findings in the literature (Anderson et al., 2020; Van den Noort et al., 2019). It will also be important to continue utilizing longitudinal studies, which are better able to distinguish between the effect of bilingualism on baseline cognition vs. cognitive decline, and to distinguish between incidence of cognitive decline as opposed to onset of cognitive decline and other dementias. In addition, future research could examine these variables in different cohorts of language speakers (i.e., English/Spanish bilinguals vs. French/Swahili bilinguals) in order to gain a more generalized understanding of bilingual-

ism on cognition.

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Effect of Physical and Conceptual Event Boundaries on Recognition-Based Memories

by Camille Scandurro '24

ABSTRACT

To understand and organize the timeline of a situation, people mentally create event models that are divided into meaningful units by event boundaries. Our study examined how event boundaries differentially affect the three levels of representation in memory for a text: surface form, textbase, and event model. The current study randomly assigned University of Notre Dame undergraduates to one of four study conditions: One Topic/One Room, One Topic/Two Rooms, Two Topics/One Room, and Two Topics/Two Rooms. After reading their assigned article, participants took a recognition-based memory test on a computer that was analyzed with signal detection theory. Our results showed that for the surface form level, people better remembered the information they had read from the second page of the articles. For the textbase level, people better remembered the general main ideas when the article contained only one topic versus two. Our results indicate that learning the same amount of information, but about two topics instead of one, suppresses memory for the second topic at the main idea level but improves memory for the second topic at the verbatim level. Because this suggests that the number of topics impedes understanding but enhances rote memorization, it could prove beneficial for educators in determining the best instructional methods to improve comprehension rather than test scores.

INTRODUCTION

Event Models

In daily life, people constantly take in and try to make sense of new information from their environments. To relate the many different qualities and characteristics of an event, we create event models, which are mental representations of the described circumstances (23). Event segmentation theory (EST) states that in order to organize information into meaningful units, people divide continuous activity into events, each marked by an event boundary (21). The goal of the current study was to investigate how event structure influences memory for newly acquired knowledge.

It has been observed that in narrative texts, the presence of event boundaries makes it more difficult to access information from the prior event. Overall, there are several lines of evidence showing that event shifts that are encountered during processing can modulate information accessibility (19).

The present study manipulated spatial shifts (e.g., moving from one room to another). Interestingly, spatial shifts can disrupt cognitive processing for some types of information (13). Updating the event model after a spatial shift leads to slower response times and a higher error rate for objects that were

encountered before the shift, known as the location updating effect.

Event Boundary Theories

The theories of event boundaries impairing memory are summarized by the Context Maintenance and Retrieval model (12). This model suggests that we associate a shared event model with objects learned close in time. Thus, recalling one object reactivates the memory trace of the other objects. Boundary-mediated memory impairment might only occur under conditions of high interference when working memory capacity is pushed to its limits, suggesting that the location updating effect depends on working memory load (8).

In contrast to this work, other research has found that after a spatial shift, retroactive interference is diminished because the multiple events portray and provide structure for the information (11). In the original research showing boundaries causing interference, an object to be remembered was represented in two event models, one in each of two rooms, and the models subsequently competed during retrieval and worsened memory. In the second case, specific word lists were given in specific rooms, leading to only one event model and no competition between lists during retrieval.

Physical and conceptual shifts

In addition to physical environmental shifts, contextual shifts can also represent event boundaries. Participants presented with stories containing either zero, one, or two event shifts were able to recall more idea units in the two-shift condition, followed by one-shift and no shift conditions (11).

Similarity between concepts surrounding a context shift might activate common semantic networks, leading to conceptual associations that bring together information from different episodic contexts (3). Learning more information about a concept also leads to faster responses for memory-based judgments, but only if the additional information is relevant in making the judgment (15). As many working memory theories based on event models have been proposed, further research is needed to parse out the particular circumstances in which event boundaries may enhance or impair memory. The current study investigated the impact of two different event boundaries on memory, both environmental context and diversity of information.

Levels of representation

Surface form, textbase, and mental/situational model are three levels of memory for a text (14). The exact, verbatim wording is represented by the surface form level of memory, whereas the textbase level represents the generalized main idea of a text. The mental model, or situational, level is the most complex and comprises the representation in memory of a situation described in a text.

Schmalhofer and Glavanov designed a recognition test approach to distinguish between the three levels of representation. In their study, participants read a complex programming

manual, followed by a recognition test in which they were presented with a sentence and chose old (verbatim) or new. New sentences were either paraphrase sentences, capturing the idea of the original text but with different wording; inference sentences, portraying new concepts not in the original text but reasonably deduced from the general principles; or wrong sentences, which detailed completely new meanings but maintained structural and syntactic similarity. The researchers used signal detection theory to compare memory performance for each of these four probes and calculated d' values based on responses of “yes” to verbatim sentences previously seen (hits) and “yes” to any of the other three probe types (false alarms).

The current study used signal detection theory and Schmalhofer and Glavanov’s approach to determine how event boundaries impact each of the three levels of memory representation for narrative text.

Current Study

There are conflicting theories surrounding event boundaries’ influence on memory. Event boundaries significantly impair semantic memory in some cases (13), and enhance it in other cases (11). In studies in which memory for narrative texts and word lists improved, a free recall test was given. In contrast, we used a recognition test to examine the different levels of representation, which is not possible with recall measures. Shifting between different event models during the recognition test might decrease accuracy (11). Most research has focused on word lists or objects, but this study presented participants with longer texts. Because not much is known about how both physical context and conceptual context relate to and impact each other, we manipulated both to understand their effects on text memory.

Competition during retrieval may lead to a decreased likelihood of remembering key points in the text, and the current study investigated how this further interacts with spatial change. The questions on our memory test assessed both main ideas and smaller details. It has been shown that frequent repetition of a topic label throughout a text leads to enhanced memory for that topic on multiple-choice based tests, regardless of where in the passage the topic label is presented (20). The current study examined whether this holds true for additional detail about the topic, not just word repetition, and whether the additional elaboration impairs memory, as previously shown. In addition to confirming that only additional relevant information is helpful in making memory-based judgments, Schul found that presenting people with an inadequate amount of information led them to create inferences from past memory (15). Therefore, participants given fewer details about a topic are likely to form more inferences than those provided with more details.

The current study had two hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: Whether a change in environment, topic, or both, event boundaries during encoding hinder memory for the learned information.

Hypothesis 2: Whether a change in environment, topic, or both, event boundaries during encoding enhance memory for the learned information.

METHODS

Participants

A total of 80 Notre Dame student participants were recruited to participate in this study via the Sona system, a website for students enrolled in classes in the Department of Psychology to participate in studies for class credit. The participants ranged in age between 18 to 22 years old ($M = 19.075$, $SD = 1.12$). They were mostly white (62.5%), with 8.75% being Asian, 20% Hispanic, 5% Black, and the remaining 3.75% responded “Other.” Additionally, 66% of participants were female. Students received one Sona class credit in exchange for their participation.

Study Phase

Study Materials

This study consisted of two parts: a study phase and a testing phase. During the study phase, participants read one of three informational articles: The Rock Cycle, Shrovetide, or Combined, which contained some of the text from each original article. Each physical, laminated article had 62 total sentences.

Study Procedure

Upon arrival at the study location, people were given a short verbal description of the study by a researcher and then presented with a consent form to read and sign. They were randomly assigned to one of eight study conditions, with 10 participants in each condition (Fig. 1). Conditions 1 and 2 made up analysis group A, conditions 3 and 4 made up analysis group B, conditions 5 and 6 were group C, and conditions 7 and 8 were group D. Participants in the “One Room” groups remained in their assigned room to read both pages of their assigned article, whereas participants in the “Two Room” groups were instructed to exit the first room and enter the second room when they had read one page of the article, whether it was on one topic or two. One room was sparsely decorated and one room had various pieces of artwork on the walls and table. In each condition, 5 participants read in the plain room and 5 read in the decorated room.

Figure 1. Participants were randomly assigned to one of eight study conditions (1-8) with four categories for analysis (a-d) based on the number of topics and rooms.

In conditions 1 and 2, the participant entered the plain or decorated room in the lab and read the first page of a printed and

laminated article about the Rock Cycle (1) or Shrovetide (2). After 3.5 minutes, the researcher took the first page and presented them with the second page. After another 3.5 minutes (7 minutes of reading in total), the researcher directed them to a separate room with a computer to take the memory test.

Conditions 3 and 4 followed an identical procedure to conditions 1 and 2, respectively, with an important distinction. When presenting the second page, the researcher directed the participant to the other room (either decorated or plain, depending on which they started with), and presented them with the second page. After another 3.5 minutes in the second room, the researcher again directed them to the separate room for the memory test. Together, conditions 3 and 4 made up one group for analysis, as they were both the one-topic, two-room groups.

Conditions 5-8 read the combined articles. In conditions 5 and 6, the participant entered the plain room or decorated room and read one page of the article, with either with the Rock Cycle page first (5) or the Shrovetide page first (6). Each page of the article contained half of the information of the longer versions, for the same total amount of information with both pages together. After 3.5 minutes, the researcher took the first page and presented them with the second page, which was about the other topic, again with half the information. After another 3.5 minutes, the researcher directed them to the separate room for the memory test. Together, conditions 5 and 6 made up one group for analysis, as they were both the two-topic, one-room groups.

Conditions 7 and 8 followed an identical procedure to conditions 5 and 6, respectively, but again were directed to enter the second room upon receiving the second page. Together, conditions 7 and 8 made up one group for analysis, as they were both the two-topic, two-room groups. The time course of the study is shown below in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Experimental design

Testing Phase

Testing Materials

The second phase of the study used a recognition-based memory test programmed with PsychoPy software (10). There were four different memory tests (Rock Cycle Long, Shrovetide Long, Combined Rock First, and Combined Shrovetide First).

People were presented with forty-eight probe sentences, from twelve sentences in the original article. There were four kinds of probes for each study item: verbatim (“*Sedimentary rocks are formed on or near the Earth’s surface from pieces of other*

existing rock or organic material”), paraphrase (“*Pieces of existing rock or organic material create sedimentary rocks, which are formed on or near the Earth’s surface*”), inference (“*Pieces of existing rock or organic material are only present at the Earth’s surface, which is why they form sedimentary rocks*”), and wrong (“*Metamorphic rocks are formed on or near the Earth’s surface from pieces of other existing rock or organic material*”).

Testing Procedure

Regardless of their condition, all participants entered a third separate room to take the memory test on a computer after they had finished reading. They clicked “True” if they thought the probe was the verbatim sentence, and “False” if they thought it was not (e.g., if it was paraphrase, inference, wrong). The instructions were, “You will be presented with sentences from the article you read. Click true if it was a sentence you read in the article.”

As stated previously, these four different probe types were used to assess differences in memory at the three levels of representation (surface form, textbase, event model) based on Schmalhofer and Glavanov’s procedure (14). At the end of the experiment, people were given a debriefing sheet about the purpose of the study, and subsequently awarded credit on SONA.

Data Analysis

To assess recognition accuracy, signal detection theory analysis was used. The d' index, which is the standardized difference between the means of the Signal Present and Signal Absent distributions, measured how accurately people discriminated hits from false alarms, with each level of memory having different protocols (14). Using only hit rates and false alarm rates, the formula for d' is: $d' = z(\text{FA}) - z(\text{H})$, where FA and H are the False Alarm and Hit rates, respectively. For surface level, a hit was when the participant answered true for a verbatim probe, and a false alarm was a true answer for a paraphrase probe. For textbase, a hit was when the participant answered true for a paraphrase probe, and a false alarm was a true answer for an inference probe. For event model, a hit was when the participant answered true for an inference probe, and a false alarm was a true answer for a wrong probe.

Three d' s were calculated for each participant for each of the three levels of representation. Overall, larger d' values indicate that participants were more accurate. Using JASP software (University of Amsterdam Department of Psychological Methods, Version 0.17.3), three 2 (order) x 2 (number of topics) x 2 (number of rooms) repeated measures ANOVAs were conducted to investigate whether a difference exists between the three conditions at each level of memory representation, as well as potential interactions between order, topics, and rooms. The alpha level was set at .05 for all analyses.

RESULTS

Consistent with the recency effect, people better remembered the information they had read from the second page (Fig. 3A).

For the surface form level of memory, the ANOVA showed a main effect of order ($F[1,76] = 6.80, p = 0.01, \eta_p^2 = 0.08$). Measuring the standardized differences between Signal Present and Signal Absent means, the marginal mean d' values for the first and second pages were $0.44 (\pm 0.110)$ and $0.80 (\pm 0.110)$, respectively. Beyond this, there were no other significant effects or interactions, all $F_s < 1$.

People were better able to remember the propositional information when it was about one topic (Fig. 3B). For the textbase level, there was a significant main effect for number of topics ($F[1,76] = 9.72, p = 0.003, \eta_p^2 = 0.11$). The mean d' value for one topic was $1.12 (\pm 0.130)$, and the mean for two topics was $0.77 (\pm 0.130)$. There was also a significant interaction between order and number of topics ($F[1,76] = 5.84, p = 0.02, \eta_p^2 = 0.07$). Breaking this interaction down, we see that with one topic, the effect of order was not significant ($F[1,76] = 1.57, p = 0.22, \eta_p^2 = 0.04$). However, with two topics, the effect of order was significant, with people remembering the first topic far better than the second ($F[1,76] = 5.00, p = 0.03, \eta_p^2 = 0.116$). This suggests that when there is only a single topic, people can continue to build their knowledge and memory. However, when there are two topics, there is a primacy effect, where memory of the first topic interferes with memory of the second.

The false alarm rate was greater than the hit rate, as indicated by the negative values for d' , which suggests lack of a deep understanding of the material (Fig. 3C). With all $F_s < 1$, no significant findings were observed at the event model level of memory ($F[1,76] = 0.111$ [Order], 0.145 [Order x Topics], 0.063 [Order x Rooms], 0.002 [Order x Topics x Rooms]).

Figure 3. Effect of number of topics and rooms on the mean d' for different levels of memory with standard error bars shown

DISCUSSION

In this experiment, we assessed the number of topics read about, the order in which they were read, and whether the reading occurred in a single context or multiple contexts, as well as how these factors may influence one another. Moreover, this assessment was made at three levels of representation, the surface form, textbase, and event model levels.

In terms of the number of topics, we found that only the textbase level was affected. There was a memory advantage when there was only one topic versus two. Specifically, textbase memory for the second topic was impaired. Thus, there is proactive interference of prior memories on memory for later information, but only at the textbase level, which is memory for the ideas in the text itself. Memory at the event model level, which would correspond more closely to understanding, was unaffected.

In terms of the number of rooms in which the materials were read, we found no significant effects. Thus, the event boundary and shift in environmental context did not play a major role in influencing memory. Instead, memory was more influenced by conceptual factors of the information itself, not the setting in which it was learned.

In terms of the order in which the topics were encountered, we found that people better remembered verbatim wording, as measured by the surface form index, from the second topic that they read. In some sense, this is the opposite of the number of topics finding at the textbase level, in that this is evidence of retroactive interference. Beyond this main effect at the surface form level, for the textbase level, a significant interaction of order and number of topics shows that people remembered the second page better than the first when they were about one topic, but remembered the first page better than the second when they were about two topics. When there are two topics, the first topic interferes with the acquisition of the second, which is known as the primacy effect.

SIGNIFICANCE AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

One goal of this study was to provide insight into the educa-

tion system, and whether it is better to learn all class subjects in one classroom, as in most elementary schools, or to separate subjects into different classrooms, as in the typical courses of high schools and universities. Our results showed that the number of rooms did not have a significant impact on memory, so classroom structure might not have a large impact on learning in school.

Interestingly, two topics suppressed memory for the second topic at the textbase level but enhanced memory for the second topic at the surface form level. This suggests that this particular conceptual event boundary compromises understanding but improves rote memorization.

However, this study had multiple limitations. The participants read two-page articles for a total of seven minutes, not long textbook chapters. Further, all participants were college students attending a prestigious university. In addition to time and demographic limitations, the study design only tested memorization, not actual understanding of the text. Nevertheless, the results provide support for the theory that event boundaries impair memory through interference mechanisms.

Future studies could test a broader participant pool of different ages and education levels. To clarify between event boundaries' influence on memorization vs. comprehension, future studies could separate people into two groups: one that simply memorized text (as in this study), and one that had to apply what they had read and create inferences.

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Approach/Avoid Compatibility Effect Among Valanced Images

by Libby O'Brien '24

ABSTRACT

The stimulus-response compatibility phenomenon, characterized by faster and more accurate responses when the stimulus and response correspond than when they do not, has been extensively studied. For example, if asked to identify the color of text, a compatible trial would involve a stimulus of the word “blue” written in blue text and a response of “blue.” An incompatible trial would involve a stimulus of the word “blue” written in red text and a response of “red.” In this scenario, one would observe faster responses when the word and color of the word are the same than when they are different. Styrkowiec and Szczepanowski’s (2013) work demonstrated this effect using colored stimuli, and Solarz’s (1960) study further exemplified this effect by investigating approach/avoid arm movements in response to valanced (evoking positive or negative emotions) stimuli. Rougier et al. (2018) refined the paradigm by using whole-body movements. This study aimed to extend the approach/avoid compatibility effect to valanced images using positive and negative images of animals. Twenty-five college students participated in a within-subjects design using the online program, PsyToolkit. Results revealed faster response times in compatible trials (approaching positive images, avoiding negative images) compared to incompatible trials. The findings suggest the generalizability of the approach/avoid compatibility effect to valanced images, prompting further exploration in different stimulus categories and sensory modalities.

APPROACH/AVOID COMPATIBILITY EFFECT AMONG VALANCED IMAGES

The stimulus-response compatibility effect refers to the phenomenon in which response times are faster and more accurate when the stimulus and response correspond than when they conflict. A classic example of this effect is shown in Styrkowiec and Szczepanowski’s (2013) study in which participants viewed a colored stimulus on a screen and were instructed to press the button corresponding to that color as fast as possible. They found that, on average, participant response times were faster when the location of the colored stimulus on the screen corresponded to the location of the corresponding button (e.g. a green block appearing on the left side of the screen and pressing the left button to indicate green) than when the stimulus and button location were opposing (eg. a green block appearing on the right side of the screen and pressing the left button to indicate green).

In Solarz’s (1960) study, he explored whether this compatibility effect applies to approach/avoid arm movements in response to positively/negatively valanced stimuli. His data revealed that, on average, participants were faster in the compatible task – pushing away cards with negative words and bringing closer cards with positive words – than in the incompatible task.

However, replicability has been an issue among these types of approach/avoid studies due to the ambiguity of arm movements. An arm flexion can constitute an approach movement in the case of bringing something closer to oneself, but it can also constitute an avoid movement in the case of withdrawing one’s hand from something.

To negate this ambiguity, Rougier et al.’s (2018) study grounds their approach/avoid compatibility task in whole body movements rather than arm movements. In their experiment, they had participants view a screen in which a positive or negative word was displayed in front of a natural background scene. In the compatible condition, subjects had to approach positive words and avoid negative words, and in the incompatible condition, they had to approach negative words and avoid positive words. Approach and avoid movements were visually simulated through key presses that zoomed in or out of the scene to simulate walking towards or away from the stimuli. They found that, on average, response times were faster in the compatible condition than in the incompatible condition.

We generalized experiment 1 from Rougier et al.’s (2018) study but with positive and negative images of animals instead of words. Like words, images have the capacity to trigger an emotional response in people, which is why we predicted that our experiment would result in the same approach/avoid compatibility effect. Based on these theoretical assumptions, we hypothesize that people will approach positive images and avoid negative images faster than the reverse. In this experiment, participants will engage in a compatibility and incompatibility task using the program PsyToolkit. In the compatibility task, participants will view a series of positive and negative images on their computer screen and will be asked to press the ‘Y’ key to approach positive images and press the ‘N’ key to avoid negative images. In the incompatibility task, participants will be asked to press the ‘N’ key to avoid positive images and press the ‘Y’ key to approach negative images. Response times and accuracies for each image will be recorded by the PsyToolkit program to determine if there is a significant difference between response times in the compatible and incompatible trials. We predict that response times for correct responses will be faster, on average, in the compatible trials than in the incompatible trials.

METHODS

Participants

Twenty-five college students ($M_{age} = 20.36$, $SD_{age} = 1.11$, 17 females) from the University of Notre Dame enrolled in PSY 30160-01 participated in this study. We utilized a within-subjects design for this experiment, such that all participants completed both the compatible block (approaching positive images and avoiding negative images) as well as the incompatible block (approaching negative images and avoiding positive images). Block order was randomly assigned by the PsyToolkit program to control for order effects, the phenomenon in which the order of the blocks could possibly affect respondents’ responses. Fourteen participants were assigned to the compat-

ible task first, followed by the incompatible task, and 11 were assigned to the reverse order.

Materials

We programmed PsyToolkit with 25 positive and 25 negative images of animals from the NAPS database (Marchewka, 2014) as our target images, such that positive images ($M = 6.31$, $SD = 1.79$) were rated as significantly more positive than negative images ($M = 4.76$, $SD = 1.75$, paired $t[49] = 2.36$, $p = 0.03$, two-tailed) on a (1 = *very negative* to 9 = *very positive* scale). Positive and negative images also differed significantly with respect to the motivational direction scale, with higher ratings for positive images ($M = 6.16$, $SD = 1.79$) than for negative images ($M = 4.74$, $SD = 1.52$), paired $t[49] = 2.29$, $p = 0.03$, two-tailed (on a 1 = *to avoid* to 9 = *to approach* scale).

Logistic Parameter	Negative Images		Positive Images		$t(49)$	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Valence Rating	4.76	0.35	6.31	0.3	2.36	0.03*
Ap/Av Rating	4.47	1.52	6.16	1.7	2.29	0.03*

* $p < .05$

Table 1. Means, standard deviation, and paired two-tailed t-test scores for Valence Ratings of Positive and Negative Images

These images were presented against a fixed background to create the perception of depth. The background and target image were zoomed in or zoomed out by 10% based on the participants' response to the stimuli. Approach movements, prompted by pressing the 'Y' key, elicited a zoom-in effect, while avoid movements, prompted by pressing the 'N' key, elicited a zoom-out effect. Consequently, whole body approach/avoid movements were visually simulated.

Procedure

All participants received a link in their email to the VAAST simulation, run through the program, PsyToolkit. The program randomly assigned participants to two different blocks, such that some participants began with the compatibility task followed by the incompatibility task, and others had the reverse order.

At the onset of the simulation, the participants were given a series of instructions. To begin each trial, they were told to press the 'H' key, which prompts an image to appear on the screen. They then had to classify the image as positive or negative by pressing the 'Y' key to approach or the 'N' key to avoid as quickly and accurately as possible. In the compatibility task, the participants were told to approach positive images and avoid negative images. Conversely, in the incompatibility task, participants were told to approach negative images and avoid

positive images. The dependent variable, response time, was recorded for each trial from the appearance of the image to the press of the 'Y' or 'N' key.

The experiment began with a practice round, in which participants practiced their first assigned task (the incompatibility task or compatibility task) with 10 images. Following the practice round, they then completed the same task with 40 images, presented in a random order. After this, the participants then completed another practice round with the same 10 practice images, this time with the opposite instructions from the first round (those who had the compatibility task first now complete the incompatibility task, and vice versa). Upon completion of this practice round, they then completed the same task with 40 images, again randomized to control for expectancy/practice effects.

RESULTS

We predicted that response times would be faster in the compatibility task than in the incompatibility task. Consistent with our prediction, the results of a paired one-tailed t-test as shown in Table 2 reveal a main effect of compatibility ($t[24] = 3.02$, $p < 0.01$), with faster average response times in the compatible trials ($M = 912.89$ ms, $SE = 35.66$ ms) than in the incompatible trials ($M = 1047.55$ ms, $SE = 52.85$ ms). Further analysis as shown in Table 3 reveal that there was no significant difference in reaction times between block order 1 and block order 2, unpaired $t(24) = 0.59$, $p = 0.56$ two-tailed.

Logistic Parameter	Compatible		Incompatible		$t(24)$	p
	M	SE	M	SE		
Reaction Time (ms)	912.89	35.66	1047.55	52.85	3.02	<0.01**

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 2. Means, standard error, and paired one-tailed t-test scores for Compatible vs Incompatible Reaction Times

Logistic Parameter	Block Order 1		Block Order 2		$t(24)$	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
RT difference (ms) in Compatible vs Incompatible trials	111.11	243.37	164.64	200.78	0.59	0.56

* $p < .05$

Table 3. Means, standard deviation, and unpaired two-tailed t-test scores for Block Order Reaction Time Differences

DISCUSSION

In our study, we attempted to generalize the findings of Rougier et al.'s (2018) study of the approach/avoid compatibility

effect with valanced words, to valanced images. While both words and images can elicit an emotional response in people, we would argue that people are much more likely to encounter and react to a scene involving living beings than they are to visuals of words, making our experiment more externally valid. As we predicted, our results indicated that the phenomenon under consideration does indeed apply to valanced images of animals. This opens the door to further experiments exploring the approach/avoid compatibility effect with other stimuli.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In psychology, no study is perfect, and ours is no exception. Participants for our study were not randomly selected from the population; rather, they were conveniently sampled from the PSY 30160-01 class at Notre Dame. As such, our findings may not reflect the general population. Additionally, when looking for confounds in our data, we found that there was a significant difference in reaction time for ‘Y’ key presses ($M = 1023.56$ ms, $SE = 46.72$) compared to ‘N’ key presses ($M = 951.95$ ms, $SE = 37.48$), paired $t(24) = 2.41$, $p = 0.02$. A future study might counterbalance the assignment of ‘N’ and ‘Y’ keys to the approach/avoid conditions to account for this discrepancy.

Logistic Parameter	‘Y’ Key		‘N’ Key		$t(24)$	p
	M	SE	M	SE		
Reaction Time (ms)	1023.56	46.72	951.95	37.48	2.41	0.02*

* $p < .05$

Table 4. Means, standard error, and paired two-tailed t-test scores for ‘Y’ key vs ‘N’ key Reaction Time

Finally, some participants expressed that some images were ambiguous as to whether they were positive or negative. Thus, a future study might select images with valence ratings closer to the extremes to reduce any confusion.

Because we found the approach/avoid compatibility effect for positive and negative images of animals, it would be interesting to explore how other categories of images (people, objects, faces, or landscapes) from the NAPS database compare. Furthermore, one could explore whether the approach/avoid compatibility effect generalizes to other sensory stimuli, such as sounds. For such an experiment, a reliable database with auditory stimuli ratings would be necessary.

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Fourier Series, Bernoulli Numbers, and the Riemann Zeta Function

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ABSTRACT

Fourier series are powerful mathematical tools that have applications across many fields. They were initially motivated by the need to solve the periodic partial differential equations appearing in physics—specifically the heat equation, wave equation, and the simple harmonic oscillator, the latter of which is the foundation of modern quantum mechanics. However, Fourier series also have surprising applications outside of periodic functions. The Riemann zeta function and Bernoulli numbers both can be calculated using Fourier series. The Riemann zeta function was famously used by Euler to demonstrate the Basel problem, and more generally can be evaluated specifically at any positive even number $2k$, the proof of which is explored in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most critical questions of thermodynamics concerns the distribution of heat in a system. We can approach this through a much simpler question: how can we model heat dispersion along an insulated metal bar with length l ? We can see that a solution $u(x, t)$, a function giving the heat at a location x at time t on the bar, must satisfy three conditions on the interval $[0, l]$:

$$\frac{du}{dt} = k \frac{d^2u}{dx^2}, \quad u(0, t) = u(l, t) = 0, \quad u(x, 0) = f(x)$$

The conditions guarantee that the endpoints of the rod start with zero heat, the initial heat is correctly modeled at time zero, and the heat dispersion obeys the heat equation. To find solutions to this equation, we use a separation of variables $u(x, t) = F(x)G(t)$. We obtain the general solutions

$$G(t) = C_0 e^{Akt}$$

$$F(x) = C_1 \cos(\lambda x) + C_2 \sin(\lambda x), \quad \lambda = \sqrt{-A}$$

Plugging the two given initial conditions and the boundary condition into the general solution gives

$$u_n(x, t) = a_n \sin\left(\frac{n\pi x}{l}\right)$$

Because the above differentials are linear operators, $u(x, t)$ will be the sum of each u_n , and therefore

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \sin\left(\frac{n\pi x}{l}\right) \quad (1)$$

For this system, the question then becomes: if we have an arbitrary initial heat dispersion $f(x)$, can we represent it as an infinite sum of sines, and how do we calculate the coefficients

a_n ? This question motivates the study of Fourier analysis. Fourier analysis concerns the study of representing functions as sums of cosines and sines, similar to how Taylor series represent functions as polynomials.

In general, if a function $f(x)$ is continuous and periodic such that $f(x) = f(x + T)$ for some period T , then f can be represented by an infinite *trigonometric polynomial* of the form

$$f(x) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [a_k \cos kx + b_k \sin kx] \quad (2)$$

To use the Fourier representation of a function, we need a method for calculating the coefficients of the series. To do so, we will define a new operation.

Definition 1.1 The *inner product* of two functions f and g is a function $\langle f, g \rangle \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfying:

- (i) *Linearity*: $\langle f_1 + f_2, g \rangle = \langle f_1, g \rangle + \langle f_2, g \rangle$ and $\langle af, g \rangle = a\langle f, g \rangle$ for a scalar $a \in \mathbb{R}$ (*Linearity*)
- (ii) *Symmetry*: $\langle f, g \rangle = \langle g, f \rangle$
- (iii) *Positive-Definiteness*: $\langle f, f \rangle > 0$ if $x \neq 0$

For our purposes, we will define the inner product of two functions on $[-\pi, \pi]$, or the $L^2([-\pi, \pi])$ inner product, to be

$$\langle f, g \rangle = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} (fg) dx$$

If $\langle f, g \rangle = 0$ on $[-\pi, \pi]$, then f and g are said to be orthogonal. Understanding the *orthogonal* relations between the trigonometric functions will prove to be important in calculating the coefficients of trigonometric polynomials of functions. When $n \neq m$,

$$\langle \cos nx, 1 \rangle = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos^2(nx) dx = 0$$

$$\langle \sin nx, 1 \rangle = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin^2(nx) dx = 0$$

$$\langle \sin nx, \sin mx \rangle = \langle \cos nx, \cos mx \rangle = \langle \cos nx, \sin mx \rangle = 0$$

Conversely, when $n = m$,

$$\langle \cos nx, \sin mx \rangle = 0$$

$$\langle \sin nx, \sin mx \rangle = \langle \cos nx, \cos mx \rangle = \pi$$

Applying the properties of inner products to the definition of the trigonometric polynomial, we see that

$$\langle f, \sin nx \rangle = \left\langle \frac{1}{2}a_0 + \sum a_k \cos kx + \sum b_k \sin kx, \sin nx \right\rangle = b_n \pi$$

$$\langle f, \cos nx \rangle = \left\langle \frac{1}{2}a_0 + \sum a_k \cos kx + \sum b_k \sin kx, \cos nx \right\rangle = a_n \pi$$

Assuming a function can be represented by an infinite trigonometric polynomial, we now have a tool at our disposal for calculating the coefficients. Hence, we see that the coefficients a_n and b_n are calculated by

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f \sin nx dx, \quad b_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f \cos nx dx \quad (3)$$

While the motivation for studying Fourier analysis is rooted in physics, Fourier analysis has a surprising application to

number theory. The *Riemann zeta function* is an important function related to prime numbers that can be better understood through the lens of Fourier analysis. It is defined such that, for all $x > 1$,

$$\zeta(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^x}$$

The connection to number theory is illustrated by the two theorems below.

Theorem 0.1. *If $d(n)$ is the number of divisors of n , then*

$$\zeta(x)^2 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{d(n)}{n^x}$$

Theorem 0.2. *If $\sigma(n)$ is the sum of the divisors of n , then*

$$\zeta(x)\zeta(x-1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sigma(n)}{n^x}$$

Prime numbers are one of the greatest focuses within number theory because of their strange distribution and behavior. In particular, understanding the solutions to this equation for complex entries is one of the most important unsolved problems in mathematics. To see how this function relates specifically to prime numbers, Euler's product formula directly expresses the function in terms of prime numbers.

Theorem 0.3. *Euler's Product Formula*

$$\zeta(x) = \prod_p \frac{1}{1-p^{-x}}, \quad x > 1$$

Proof. To prove this relation, fix $x > 1$ and take integers $M > N \geq 2$. Then,

$$\prod_{p \leq N} \left(\frac{1}{p^x} + \frac{1}{p^{2x}} + \frac{1}{p^{3x}} + \dots + \frac{1}{p^{Mx}} \right) \leq \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^x} = \zeta(x)$$

First, let $M \rightarrow \infty$

$$\prod_{p \leq N} \frac{1}{1-p^{-x}} \leq \zeta(x)$$

The infinite products must converge, thus

$$\prod_p \frac{1}{1-p^{-x}} \leq \zeta(x)$$

Similarly, we take $M > N \geq 2$ to obtain

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{n^x} \leq \prod_{p \leq N} \left(\frac{1}{p^x} + \frac{1}{p^{2x}} + \frac{1}{p^{3x}} + \dots + \frac{1}{p^{Mx}} \right) \leq \prod_{p \leq N} \frac{1}{1-p^{-x}} \leq \prod_p \frac{1}{1-p^{-x}}$$

By letting $N \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\zeta(x) \leq \prod_p \frac{1}{1-p^{-x}}$$

Even though the Riemann zeta function is initially defined for all $x > 1$, it can be extended for all $x > 0$ using complex numbers. To do so, we first need to define the *Gamma function*

$$\Gamma(x) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-u} u^{x-1} du, \quad x > 0$$

Taking $u = nt$, it can be rewritten as

$$\Gamma(x) = n^x \int_0^{\infty} e^{-nt} t^{x-1} dt, \quad x > 0, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}$$

The Gamma function is another important function in mathematics. In fact, it is a continuous extension of the function $f(x) = (x-1)!$ where f is defined over the positive integers. By multiplying this function by the Riemann zeta function, we will be able to extend the domain of the Riemann zeta function. By summing over each n , making use of the geometric series for $\sum e^{-nx}$, and considering that the interchange of summation and integration is justified by the conditions of each function, it can be shown that

$$\Gamma(x)\zeta(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-nt} t^{x-1} dt = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{t^{x-1}}{e^t - 1} dt$$

Despite our initial assumption that $x > 1$, we recognize that

$$\int_0^1 t^{x-2} dt = \frac{1}{x-1}, \quad x > 1$$

$$\Rightarrow \Gamma(x)\zeta(x) = \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{e^t - 1} - \frac{1}{t} \right) t^{x-1} dt + \frac{1}{x-1} + \int_1^{\infty} \frac{t^{x-1}}{e^t - 1} dt$$

We notice that the right-hand side of our derived equation is well-defined and continuous on $x > 0$ except at $x = 1$. Thus, we can extend the Riemann zeta function to be defined for all real numbers on this interval. In other words, since the zeta function is *holomorphic* (differentiable on \mathbb{C} when $\text{Re}\{z\} > 1$), there is a unique way to extend the function to \mathbb{C} . It is important to note that there is a pole when $\text{Re}\{z\} = 1$ because the function diverges, so we cannot calculate certain values of the function. However, we can do better and extend the Riemann zeta function to more values. Leveraging the Fourier series of the square wave and an integral based on the Gamma function, we can construct the functional equation

$$\pi^{-x/2} \Gamma\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) \zeta(x) = \pi^{(x-1)/2} \Gamma\left(\frac{1-x}{2}\right) \zeta(1-x)$$

which defines the Riemann zeta function on the entire complex plane except at the pole. This equation reveals interesting yet odd properties of the function. For instance, for each positive integer n , $\zeta(-2n) = 0$. Additionally, $\zeta(-1) = -1/12$, which has a popular false interpretation that

$$1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + \dots = \frac{-1}{12}$$

The Riemann zeta function can be more easily evaluated with a sequence called the *Bernoulli numbers*. First, we will introduce this sequence and explain some fundamental properties before coming to this conclusion. The Bernoulli numbers originate from evaluations of the partial sums for the series $\sum k^p = 1^p + 2^p + 3^p + \dots$. However, we will instead discuss an alternate method of defining this sequence. Define the generating function for B_n according to the following Taylor series:

$$\frac{x}{e^x - 1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_n}{n!} x^n$$

Evaluating for the polynomial representation of $e^x - 1$ and dividing the fraction by x , it follows that

$$e^x - 1 = x + \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^3}{3!} + \dots \Rightarrow \frac{x}{e^x - 1} = \frac{1}{1 + (\frac{1}{2}x + \frac{1}{6}x^2 + \dots)}$$

The infinite sum $1/(1+x) = 1 - x + x^2 - x^3 + \dots$ can demonstrate that, by evaluating for like coefficients, the generating function can be written as

$$\Rightarrow \frac{x}{e^x - 1} = 1 - \frac{1}{2}x + \frac{1}{12}x^2 + \dots$$

Hence, we can define $B_0 = 1, B_1 = -1/2, B_2 = 1/6$, and so on, by attributing each to a function f such that

$$f(x) = \frac{x}{e^x - 1} - \frac{x}{2} = 1 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{B_n}{n!} x^n$$

If the terms B_0 and B_1 are isolated, it is apparent that f is an even function, so for any $n \geq 1, B_{2n+1} = 0$. Multiplying the generating function by the function $e^x - 1$,

$$(e^x - 1)\left(\frac{x}{e^x - 1}\right) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_n}{n!} x^n \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n!} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c_n x^n$$

Such that

$$c_n = \frac{B_0}{0!n!} + \frac{B_1}{1!(n-1)!} + \dots + \frac{B_{n-1}}{(n-1)!1!}$$

Because the sum is equal to function x , the only non-zero coefficient will be $c_1 = 1$. Therefore, analyzing the other terms,

$$c_n = 0 \Rightarrow \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{n}{k} B_k = 0, \quad n \geq 2$$

Hence, by further calculation, $B_4 = -1/30, B_6 = 1/42, B_8 = -1/30$, and so on. A pattern starts appearing such that these terms alternate in sign. This will be generally shown to be true as a corollary to the next theorem.

RESULTS

Euler famously demonstrated that $\zeta(2) = 1/n^2 = \pi^2/6$, known as the *Basel problem*. However, he would soon demonstrate a more general result for any positive even number $2k$. Using the Bernoulli numbers, there is a very elegant result, stated in the theorem below.

Theorem 0.4. For any integer $k \geq 1$,

$$\zeta(2k) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{2k}} = (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(2\pi)^{2k}}{2(2k)!} B_{2k}$$

Proof. By taking the corresponding Fourier series of $\cos cx$ where c is excluded from Z ,

$$\cos c\pi = \frac{\sin c\pi}{c\pi} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2c \sin c\pi}{\pi(c^2 - n^2)}$$

Multiply by $c\pi/\sin(c\pi)$

$$c\pi \cot c\pi = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2c^2}{c^2 - n^2} = 1 - 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{c^2}{n^2 - c^2}$$

The sum then begins to take the form of a geometric series. By dividing each term within the fraction by $1/n^2$,

$$= 1 - 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(c/n)^2}{1 - (c/n)^2} = 1 - 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{c}{n}\right)^{2k} = 1 - 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (c^{2k}) \left(\frac{1}{n^{2k}}\right)$$

The interchange of sums is justified by the fact that it will converge to some finite value. $\cot c\pi$ only diverges if c is an integer, which it is strictly defined not to be. Hence, using the definition of the zeta function, the equation can be rewritten as

$$c\pi \cot c\pi = 1 - 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} c^{2k} \zeta(2k)$$

This will be compared to another representation of the function. Using the previously-mentioned Euler's formula,

$$e^{iz} = \cos z + i \sin z, \quad e^{-iz} = \cos z - i \sin z$$

Some rearrangement of terms shows that

$$\cos z = \frac{e^{iz} + e^{-iz}}{2}, \quad \sin z = \frac{e^{iz} - e^{-iz}}{2i} \Rightarrow \cot z = i \left(\frac{e^{iz} + e^{-iz}}{e^{iz} - e^{-iz}} \right)$$

Manipulating the denominator redefines the function as

$$\cot z = i \left(1 + \frac{2}{e^{2iz} - 1} \right) \Rightarrow z \cot z = iz + \frac{2iz}{e^{2iz} - 1}$$

Using the generating function for Bernoulli numbers,

$$\frac{x}{e^x - 1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_n}{n!} x^n \Rightarrow \frac{x}{e^x - 1} + \frac{1}{2}x = 1 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{B_n}{n!} x^n$$

Set $x = 2iz$. Then,

$$iz + \frac{2iz}{e^{2iz} - 1} = 1 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{B_n}{n!} (2iz)^n = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{B_{2k}}{(2k)!} (2iz)^{2k}$$

Since the odd Bernoulli numbers equal 0. Factoring out the power of i ,

$$z \cot z = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{B_{2k}}{(2k)!} (2z)^{2k}$$

Finally, let $z = c\pi$. Then, separating the exponents, the final function can be written as

$$c\pi \cot c\pi = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{B_{2k}}{(2k)!} (2\pi)^{2k} c^{2k}$$

Because both functional representations take on a similar form save their constants, it is possible to compare the two to each other. Hence,

$$-2\zeta(2k) = (-1)^k \frac{(2\pi)^{2k}}{(2k)!} B_{2k} \Rightarrow \zeta(2k) = (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(2\pi)^{2k}}{2(2k)!} B_{2k}$$

The project aimed to first get a comprehensive introduction to Fourier series and get a glimpse into the Riemann zeta function and Bernoulli numbers. We also reviewed a method to compute the Riemann zeta function using the Fourier series of $\cos(cx)$ and Bernoulli Numbers. Some interesting future extensions of this project could be exploring the relation to the gamma function further and see if we can compute other values of the Zeta function from there, or using the Bernoulli numbers in combination with their properties to deduce the values of different types of series.

Rotation Groups: SO(2), SO(3), SU(2) Case Studies

by **Adriana Baniecki** '26

ABSTRACT

Noether's Theorem states that any symmetry in physics corresponds to a conservation law, and groups are the mathematical tools that can be used to express those symmetries. For example, SO(3) expresses conservation of angular momentum, SU(2) represents the spin of an electron, and SU(3)xSU(2)xU(1) describes strong, weak, and electromagnetic interactions. Thus, it is in the best interest of theoretical physicists to probe the structure of the SO(N) and SU(N) groups.

INTRODUCTION

Definition 0.1: A group G is defined by a collection of group elements (g) and a composition operator (\circ) such that,

$$\forall g_1, g_2 \in G, g_2 \circ g_1 \in G.$$

The composition operator satisfies the following:

1. **Associativity:** $(g_\alpha \cdot g_\beta) \cdot g_\gamma = g_\alpha \cdot (g_\beta \cdot g_\gamma)$
2. **Existence of the Identity:** $\exists I \in G$ such that $I \cdot g_\alpha = g_\alpha \cdot I = g_\alpha$.
3. **Existence of the Inverse:** $\forall g_\alpha \in G, \exists g_\alpha^{-1}$ such that $g_\alpha^{-1} \cdot g_\alpha = g_\alpha \cdot g_\alpha^{-1} = I$.

For rotation groups, group element g_1 might be the abstract concept of "rotation by 30 degrees around the x-axis" and element g_2 might be "rotation by 20 degrees around the y-axis." Using the above definition of the composition operator, acting group element g_1 and then group element g_2 is the same as acting group element $g_2 \circ g_1$ (conceptually, "rotation by 30 degrees around the x-axis and 30 degrees around the y-axis").

We wish for group elements to "act upon" some collection of objects—say x , y , and z coordinates—that are grouped into a column vector. If we represent the group elements g_1 and g_2 by matrices $D(g_1)$ and $D(g_2)$, then the abstract concept of "action" becomes computationally concrete matrix multiplication. This is known as representation theory. Additionally, representation theory preserves the definition of a composition. The product of two matrix representations, $D(g_1) \cdot D(g_2)$, produces a matrix which is the representation of the composition of the two elements, namely $D(g_2 \circ g_1)$.

It is important to note that the size of the representation depends on how many objects are in the vector. For example, consider two different representations of element g : $D(g_1)$ and $D'(g_1)$, where $D'(g_1) = S^{-1}D(g)S$. Although $D(g_1)$ and $D'(g_1)$ have different entries, they are representations of the same dimension and conceptually refer to the same abstract group element. Such representations are called *equivalent*.

Any group G has a trivial 1-dimensional representation, where $D^1(g) = 1, \forall g \in G$. This is a representation because, for any

group elements $g_1, g_2, D(g_1)D(g_2) = 1 \cdot 1 = 1 = D(g_1 \cdot g_2)$. For the rotation groups SO(N) and SU(N), the fundamental representation of any rotation element is an NxN matrix.

RESULT I: SO(2)

The group SO(2) is the group of all rotations in the xy plane. For any point in the plane, compile its two coordinate objects into a vector (x, y) . If this vector is acted upon by a group element that "rotates the vector by θ ," then $(x', y') = (x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta, -x \sin \theta + y \cos \theta)$. This group element has a 2-dimensional representation $R(\theta)$, such that

$$R(\theta) := \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

This rotation must preserve the length of the vector. If $p = (x, y)$ and $p' = (x', y')$, then

$$p'^T p' = p^T p \implies R^T R = I \quad (2)$$

This equation reveals that R must be orthogonal, which is confirmed in Equation 1. Taking the determinant of both sides of Equation 2 and using the orthogonal nature of R to conclude that $\det R = \det R^T$, then

$$\det(R^T R) = 1 \implies \det(R) = 1 \quad (3)$$

Equations 2 and 3 are the two fundamental properties of the rotation group SO(2), and both of them extend generally to SO(N).

SO(2) is a continuous group. In other words, if g is the group element describing "rotation by θ ," then θ can take any value. When $\theta \approx 0$, there is almost no rotation at all. Thus, we can approximate $R = I + J\theta$. If we want to find the 2-dimensional, irreducible, fundamental representation of SO(2), then I is the 2x2 identity matrix and J is an unknown 2x2 matrix. The Taylor series expansions for $\sin \theta$ and $\cos \theta$ give

$$R(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \frac{\theta^2}{2} \dots & \theta - \frac{\theta^3}{3} \dots \\ -\theta + \frac{\theta^3}{3} \dots & 1 - \frac{\theta^2}{2} \dots \end{pmatrix} \approx \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} + \theta \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Thus, since $R \approx I + \theta J$, the matrix J is given by

$$J = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Now, consider the group element represented by $R(\theta)$ where $\theta \gg 0$. We wish to consider the representation of a "rotation by $\theta + d\theta$," where $d\theta \ll 1$, which can be written as

$$R(\theta + d\theta) = R(\theta)R(d\theta) = R(\theta)(1 + Jd\theta)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{R(\theta + d\theta) - R(\theta)}{d\theta} &= R(\theta)J \\ \lim_{d\theta \rightarrow 0} \frac{R(\theta + d\theta) - R(\theta)}{d\theta} &= \lim_{d\theta \rightarrow 0} R(\theta)J \\ \frac{dR(\theta)}{d\theta} &= R(\theta)J \implies R(\theta) = e^{J\theta} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

This calculation shows that we can use the single matrix J to represent any 2-dimensional rotation by any angle θ . This single matrix describes every group element, and hence it is known as the group's *generator*.

RESULT II: SO(3)

The next logical step is to investigate SO(3), the group of 3-dimensional rotations. It is also important for length to be preserved under rotation in this group; as a result, Equation 2 holds. For small θ , we can once again use the approximation $R = I + J$. However, as we are now interested in the fundamental representation of SO(3), I is the 3x3 identity and J is an unknown 3x3 matrix. Substituting this small angle approximation into Equation 2 shows that $J^T = -J$, which reveals that J is a 3x3 antisymmetric matrix whose determinant is 1. Any antisymmetric matrix can be written as a combination of the three antisymmetric matrices below, and thus the three generators of SO(3) are

$$J_x = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad J_y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad J_z = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Thus, since there are three generators, the matrix R can be written as

$$R = e^{\theta_x J_x + \theta_y J_y + \theta_z J_z} = e^{\theta_i J_i}$$

Since there are now three generators, we wish to know how they relate to each other. To do this, however, we need to first establish the idea of a commutator. Say we have two representations of infinitesimal rotations, $R = I + A$ and $R' = I + B$. Then, let us investigate what happens when we apply R' to R and then undo that application (by applying R^{-1})

$$\begin{aligned} RR'R^{-1} &= (I + A)(I + B)(I + A)^{-1} \\ &\approx (I + A)(I + B)(I - A) = I + B - BA - AA + AB - ABA \end{aligned}$$

Because these rotations are infinitesimally small, then $AA \approx 0$ and $ABA \approx 0$, so the expression above becomes

$$RR'R^{-1} = I + B + AB - BA$$

This expression differs from R' by

$$RR'R^{-1} - R' = AB - BA := [A, B]$$

The expression $[A, B]$ is known as the commutator of A and B .

Now, assume that A and B are both members of the group SO(3), so that they can be written as $A = i\Sigma_i\theta_i J_i$, $B = i\Sigma_j\theta'_j J_j$.

Then, the commutator of A and B can be written as

$$[A, B] = i^2 \Sigma_i \theta_i J_i \Sigma_j \theta'_j J_j - i^2 \Sigma_j \theta'_j J_j \Sigma_i \theta_i J_i = i^2 \Sigma_{ij} \theta_i \theta'_j [J_i, J_j]$$

Thus, it suffices to calculate the commutator between the generators to understand how any two rotations commute. Brute force calculation reveals that

$$[J_x, J_y] = iJ_z \quad [J_y, J_z] = -iJ_x$$

If we define the antisymmetric symbol ϵ_{ijk} such that $\epsilon_{123} = 1$ and any index swap changes the sign, then the general commutator among generators can be expressed as

$$[J_i, J_j] = i\epsilon_{ijk} J_k \quad (6)$$

In general, a Lie group is defined to be a group where the commutator of the generators is a linear combination of the other generators such that $[Ta, Tb] = if_{abc} T_c$, where f_{abc} is the structure constant of the Lie group. Since J_x, J_y , and J_z follow this Lie algebra, with structure constant of ϵ_{ijk} , then SO(3) is a Lie group.

Thus, for a group element g in the group SO(3), we can clearly construct a 3-dimensional representation. However, we can also create an 8-dimensional representation $D^8(g)$ of the group element g in SO(3) by composing known representations in a block-diagonal matrix

$$D^8(g) = \begin{pmatrix} D^1(g) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & D^1(g) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & D^3(g) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & D^3(g) \end{pmatrix}$$

Since multiplying $D^8(g_1)$ by $D^8(g_2)$ gives the block-diagonal representing $D^8(g_2 g_1)$, then D^8 is indeed a representation. This 8-dimensional representation is a reducible representation, written as $D^8(g) = D^1(g) \oplus D^1(g) \oplus D^3(g) \oplus D^3(g)$.

In order to construct other irreducible representations of SO(3), we need to make use of tensors. To construct the 3-dimensional representation of group element g in SO(3), we envisioned g acting on a collection of three objects (coordinates) \vec{V} , whereby the representation rotated the vector \vec{V} into \vec{V}' . As a result of this rotation, the i -th component of V'

is produced by the elements of a rotation matrix R_{ij} (where $i, j \in [1, n]$) acting on the elements of the original vector V^j (where $j \in [1, n]$). This process can be written as

$$V^i \rightarrow V'^i = \sum_{j=1}^N R^{ij} V^j = R^{ij} V^j \quad (7)$$

Now suppose we wish, instead, to enact “a rotation in three dimensions” on a composition of two vectors, written as

$$\vec{v}_1 \otimes \vec{v}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} d \\ e \\ f \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} ad \\ ae \\ af \\ bd \\ be \\ bf \\ cd \\ ce \\ cf \end{pmatrix} := \begin{pmatrix} T^{11} \\ T^{12} \\ T^{13} \\ T^{21} \\ T^{22} \\ T^{23} \\ T^{31} \\ T^{32} \\ T^{33} \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Thus, we need to construct a 9-dimensional representation of “a rotation in three dimensions.” While we could view the product $\vec{v}_1 \otimes \vec{v}_2$ above as a 1-dimensional tensor T^m where $m = 1, \dots, 9$, it can also be viewed as a 2-dimensional tensor T^{ij} where $i, j \in [1, 2, 3]$. Generalizing Equation 7, tensors transform under rotation as

$$T^{ij} \rightarrow T'^{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{l=1}^N R^{ik} R^{jl} T^{kl} = R^{ik} R^{jl} T^{kl} \quad (9)$$

Thus, we can construct a 9-dimensional representation of $SO(3)$, denoted by $D(R)$. To verify that this is a representation, transform T^{ij} under two rotations R_1 and R_2 to find

$$T^{ij} \rightarrow T'^{ij} = R_1^{ik} R_1^{jl} T^{kl}$$

$$T'^{ij} \rightarrow T''^{ij} = R_2^{ik} R_2^{jl} (T'^{kl}) = R_2^{ik} R_1^{km} R_2^{ln} R_1^{mn} T^{mn} = (R_2 R_1)^{im} (R_2 R_1)^{jn} T^{mn}$$

Thus, $D(R_2)D(R_1) = D(R_2 R_1)$ and therefore T^{ij} is a valid 9-dimensional representation.

Returning to the original question, is this 9x9 representation reducible or irreducible? Consider the tensor $A^{ij} := T^{ij} - T^{ji}$, which is antisymmetric since $A^{ij} = -A^{ji}$. This tensor transforms under a rotation R by the following

$$\begin{aligned} A^{ij} \rightarrow A'^{ij} &:= T'^{ij} - T'^{ji} = R^{ik} R^{jl} T^{kl} - R^{jk} R^{il} T^{kl} \\ &= R^{ik} R^{jl} T^{kl} - R^{jl} R^{ik} T^{lk} = R^{ik} R^{jl} (T^{kl} - T^{lk}) = R^{ik} R^{jl} A^{kl} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, an antisymmetric tensor transforms into a linear combination of other antisymmetric tensors, so A^{ij} is the form of a smaller, irreducible representation of $SO(3)$. This tensor A^{ij} has three options for index i and two options for index j .

Since $A^{12} = -A^{21}$, we divide by two to avoid double-counting and conclude that three elements of the nine elements of tensor T^{ij} sit in their own irreducible representation.

Next, consider the object $S^{ij} := T^{ij} + T^{ji}$, which is symmetric since $S^{ij} = S^{ji}$. If we transform S^{ij} by a rotation R , we find that

$$S^{ij} \rightarrow S'^{ij} = R^{ik} R^{jl} S^{kl}$$

Using similar logic as above, symmetric tensors also form an irreducible representation of $SO(3)$. There are three options for S^{ij} where $i \neq j$ and three more options where $i = j$, so six elements of tensor T^{ij} sit in another irreducible representation.

However, symmetric tensors of the form S_{ii} form another irreducible representation. The tensor S_{ii} transforms under rotation in the following way

$$S^{ii} \rightarrow S'^{ii} = R^{ik} R^{il} S^{kl} = (R^T)^{ki} R^{il} S^{kl} = (R^{-1})^{ki} R^{il} S^{kl} = \delta^{kl} S^{kl} = S^{kk}$$

The above Einstein summation notation reveals that

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 S^{ii} = \sum_{k=1}^3 S^{kk}.$$

In other words, the trace of $SO(3)$ does not transform at all, and it is a 1x1 irreducible, *invariant* representation of $SO(3)$.

Thus, the 9-dimensional representation can be decomposed into a block-diagonal matrix

$$S^{-1}D(R)S = \begin{pmatrix} (1 \times 1) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & (3 \times 3) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (5 \times 5) \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

In this basis, the tensor in Equation 8 has one invariant component (given by the traditional inner product $\langle g_1, g_2 \rangle$), three antisymmetric components (represented by the traditional cross product $g_1 \times g_2$), and five symmetric components (represented by an outer product). Thus, for $SO(3)$, $9 = 1 \oplus 3 \oplus 5$.

RESULT III: SU(3)

The group $SU(2)$ consists of rotations in the 2-dimensional complex plane. Now, however, to preserve the length of vector v as it rotates into vector v' , $(v_1)^\dagger v_1 = (v'_1)^\dagger v'_1$.

Thus, the equivalent length preservation statement for $SU(N)$ groups is

$$U^\dagger U = I \quad (11)$$

Taking the determinant of both sides gives $|\det(U)|^2 = 1$, which is the defining condition for the group of unitary matrices $U(N)$. The group $SU(N)$ is defined by the more restrictive condition

$$\det U = 1 \quad (12)$$

Thus, when we find a fundamental, N -dimensional represen-

tation for an element g in $SU(N)$, we need to understand the transformation of the complex conjugate of the representation. Assuming that $SU(N)$ is similar to $SO(N)$, we can construct an initial attempt at a 1-dimensional tensor representation and take its complex conjugate in the following way

$$\psi^i \rightarrow \sum_{k=1}^N U^{ij} \psi^j = U^{ij} \psi^j \quad (13)$$

$$\psi^{i*} \rightarrow (U^{ij})^* (\psi^j)^* = (U^{T*})^{ji} (\psi^j)^* = (U^\dagger)^{ji} (\psi^j)^* \quad (14)$$

At this point, it is helpful to introduce the following notation convention: $\psi_i := \psi^{i*}$.

Using lower indices, Equations 13 and 14 become

$$\psi^i \rightarrow \psi'^i = U_j^i \psi^j \quad (15)$$

$$\psi_i \rightarrow \psi'_i = \psi_j (U^\dagger)_i^j \quad (16)$$

This process can be extrapolated to construct higher-dimension representations of $SU(N)$ groups by using tensors in the following way

$$\phi_k^{ij} \rightarrow \phi'_k{}^{ij} = U_i^i U_j^j (U^\dagger)_k^n \phi_n^{lm}$$

While this notation may look intimidating, the key takeaway is that the structure follows the revelation from Equations 13 and 14: the tensor ϕ transforms according to U and its complex conjugate ϕ^* transforms according to U^\dagger . Thus the upper indices i, j transform according to two U matrices with upper indices U_i^i, U_j^j ; similarly, the lower index k transforms according to a U^\dagger matrix with lower index $(U^\dagger)_k$.

Next, we can find the $SU(N)$ generators similarly to $SO(N)$. For a small rotation angle, we can approximate $U \approx I + iH$, where H is the generator we are seeking. Plugging this approximation into Equation 11 and keeping only leading-order terms, we find that

$$U^\dagger U = (I + iH)^\dagger (I + iH) = I$$

$$I - i(H^\dagger - H) = I \implies H^\dagger = H$$

In other words, H is a $N \times N$ Hermitian matrix. Thus, for any angle, $U = e^{iH}$. We can use the fact that H can be diagonalized to write $H = C^\dagger DC$, and then compute the determinant of U to be

$$\det U = \det e^{iH} = \det e^{i(C^\dagger DC)} = \det e^{iD} = e^{i \operatorname{tr} H}$$

Because Equation 12 states that $\det U = I$, then $\operatorname{tr} H = 0$. In summary, H is an $N \times N$ traceless Hermitian matrix. For the 2-dimensional, fundamental, irreducible representation of $SU(2)$, any H can be written in terms of the three Pauli matrices below

$$\sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

Therefore, any abstract group element in $SU(2)$ can be written as an exponential combination of the generators, as stated below in Einstein summation notation

$$U = e^{i\theta_1 \sigma_1 + i\theta_2 \sigma_2 + i\theta_3 \sigma_3} = e^{i\theta_a \sigma_a}$$

Next, we can brute-force compute the Lie algebra between the $SU(2)$ generators to find that

$$[\sigma_i, \sigma_j] = 2i\epsilon_{ijk} \sigma_k$$

For historical reasons (which we will discover momentarily), it is preferred to define the generators with a $1/2$ constant so that the general form and Lie Algebra becomes

$$U = e^{\frac{i}{2} \theta_a \sigma_a} \quad (18)$$

$$[\sigma_i, \sigma_j] = i\epsilon_{ijk} \sigma_k \quad (19)$$

DISCUSSION

After exploring these groups, we find that the Lie algebra of $SO(3)$ and $SU(2)$ are identical. This means that $SU(2)$ is locally isomorphic to $SO(3)$ for small angles θ . Thus, for $SU(2)$, upper and lower indices must transform in the same way, because these transformations are the same as a transformation in $SO(3)$.

We can investigate the larger structure of both groups by using the generators J_x, J_y and J_z to compute an $SO(3)$ matrix representing a rotation of $\theta_z = 2\pi$

$$R = e^{\theta_x J_x + \theta_y J_y + \theta_z J_z} = e^{2\pi J_z} = \cos(2\pi)I + \sin(2\pi)J_z = I$$

Now, use the generators σ_1, σ_2 , and σ_3 to compute an $SU(2)$ matrix representing a rotation of $\theta_3 = 2\pi$

$$U = e^{\frac{i}{2} \theta_1 \sigma_1 + \frac{i}{2} \theta_2 \sigma_2 + \frac{i}{2} \theta_3 \sigma_3} = e^{\frac{i}{2} 2\pi \sigma_3} = \cos(\pi)I + \sin(\pi)J_z = -I$$

Thus, for the same angle $\theta = 2\pi$, $SU(2)$ only goes halfway around and $SO(3)$ goes completely around. In other words, $SU(2)$ double-covers $SO(3)$. In conclusion, any rotation in $SU(2)$ —such as the spin of an electron—can be visualized as a rotation in $SO(3)$.

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College of Science Student Spotlights

Connor Smith, 2026

Major: Physics

How did you become interested and involved in this field of study?

My interest in astrophysics and astronomy started at a very young age. My family always likes to joke about this fact, bringing up a video from my kindergarten graduation where each student was asked what they wanted to be when they grew up. Everyone was giving answers like firefighter or professional baseball player, but I, without hesitation, said astronomer. I never really looked back. I came into Notre Dame as a Physics major and each interaction I've had with the field through classes, professors, and research has only confirmed to me that I am on the right path. I've always been fascinated not just about general physics, but specifically the study of space. I loved going to NASA as a kid and consistently watched shows or documentaries about space travel and astronomy. I joined Professor Nguyen's research group on gravitational waves and dark matter this past Fall, after deciding to branch out from the experimental side of research into the theoretical. I noticed that her research dealt with binary compact objects (black holes and neutron stars). As a kid, I had long been fascinated by the mystery of black holes and jumped at the opportunity to participate in research pertaining to their study.

What research have you conducted during your time in undergrad?

In my time as an undergrad, I have participated in two separate research groups. I work with Professor Crepp in his adaptive optics lab, studying the non-linear curvature wavefront sensor (nlCWFS) and its performance in the presence of atmospheric turbulence. Most of my work with the group involved MATLAB simulations to test various meth-

ods of centroiding images, as the ability to correctly determine the center of the image is vital for real-time corrections to be made by a deformable mirror in the adaptive optics system. I performed both timing and accuracy analyses of various centroiding methods to help determine which method provided the best trade-off between performance accuracy and runtime. I also spent a portion of my time in the lab, assembling and upgrading the optics system as new parts came in and the system required realignment. In addition to experimental research with Professor Crepp, I also participate in theoretical research with Professor Nguyen. The main focus of my research with Professor Nguyen has been conducting parameter estimations for various gravitational wave events. These events are the result of mergers between binary black holes, binary neutron stars, and binary black hole neutron star pairs. Using data collected by the LVK laser interferometer collaboration, I use the bilby parameter estimation library in python to estimate various values related to the black holes or neutron stars that generated the gravitational wave event. Calculating these different values provides us with a greater understanding of the compact objects and provides a framework through which we can begin interpreting dark matter interactions. In the future, we hope to incorporate various dark matter models into the parameter estimation code to gain a greater understanding of different ways dark matter could potentially interact or be detected.

What is your favorite thing about research?

My favorite thing about research is the fact that it is always new. Research never stops. I have always been someone who loves to learn. I often joke with my friends that if there was a job that paid you for being a student, where you could just sit and learn anything about everything, I would take it. Conducting research is probably the closest I can get to having a job like that. Each day is pushing the boundary of what we know and investigating new phenomena. I love research because it gives me the chance to consistently be learning about a field that

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I enjoy and engaging my curiosity about the world around me. When I say that research is always new, I mean that it constantly provides opportunities to learn new things and gain a deeper understanding of the world around us.

What are your career goals and how do you hope to incorporate what you have learned from research in your future work?

My plan after graduation is to go straight into graduate school and earn a Ph.D. in astrophysics. After that, I would love to have the opportunity to work in a research-based profession either at an institution like NASA, an observatory, or as a research and teaching professor at a university. My research has taught me how to look for solutions or begin an investigation on a topic when there was no clear question to begin from. By pursuing a field based in research, I hope to be able to spend each day as a student in some sense, learning things previously unknown.

Morgan Blakey, 2025

Major: Neuroscience and Behavior

How did you become interested and involved in this field of study?

Growing up watching my grandfather suffer from Alzheimer's was heartbreaking. Alzheimer's not only affected his memory but also affected his physical abilities. As a child, I would always ask questions and come up with ideas as to how to help my grandfather, but at that time, it was difficult for me to understand how Alzheimer's affects a person. As I got older, I wanted to combine my passion for biological concepts and psychology to investigate this disease further, which led me to discover Neuroscience. Neuroscience was fascinating because it allowed me to satisfy my curious mind as I got older

by enabling me to understand the brain and how it works, which I learned helps us better understand ourselves and others.

What research have you conducted during your time in undergrad?

Throughout my time as an undergrad, I have had the privilege of conducting two summer research projects. My first research project was at the University of Minnesota where I had the opportunity to do research in a lab focusing on neonatal iron nutrition and metabolism and the developing brain, specifically the hippocampus, which underlies recognition and memory processing. My project aimed to see how the gene BDNF (variants 4 and 6) of the hippocampus responds to increasing severity and duration of Iron Deficiency. In this project, the techniques that I used were qPCR, RNA isolation, cDNA Isolation, and cell culture. My second research project took place at Columbia University, where I gained a unique perspective through researching underrepresented populations. My project specifically aimed to understand the effects of Hypertension and High Blood Pressure on White matter hyperintensities in Black and Latinx communities specifically accounting for sex/gender. During this research project, I learned skills about statistical analysis specifically using the programming platform R to do multiple linear regression analyses. I am also a part of the ASSIST lab with Dr. Ammerman, which has allowed me to continue my research involving neuroscience and psychology.

What is your favorite thing about research?

My favorite aspect of research is the chance to exercise creativity and bring my ideas to life. Research not only allows me to delve into the intricacies of various processes on Earth, but also to find innovative approaches to comprehend those processes.

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What are your career goals and how do you hope to incorporate what you have learned from research in your future work?

My career goal is to be a Neurologist and I hope to incorporate the research that I have learned in the future to understand my patient's health issues better. Along with my goal of becoming a neurologist, I also want to continue to do research and help make sure that underrepresented populations have a voice in research especially when there are neurological diseases such as Alzheimer's that occur as a silent epidemic in these populations. Overall, the research that I have done in neuroscience has allowed me to be able to understand the health conditions, especially of those like my grandfather, and understand what processes and mechanisms are at play when diseases like Alzheimer's occur.

Zhaohan Zhu, 2024

Major: Biological Sciences

How did you become interested and involved in this field of study?

I always had an interest in biology, especially figuring out how the different biological systems worked. However, it was not until taking AP

Biology in high school that I truly became involved. My teacher was very motivated and made learning about biology extremely fun, which led to me deciding to pursue it further in college.

What research have you conducted during your time in undergrad?

In undergrad I have done 3 major research projects. In Dr. Hyde's lab, I have researched on the zebrafish retina and its ability to regenerate. We focused on characterizing the effects of the immune response on different types of retina damage in order to gain an understanding in its application in human retina diseases. For this research, I have learned zebrafish

breeding/maintenance, cryosectioning, immunohistochemistry, and confocal microscopy. During the summer, I have done two internships at St. Jude and performed research projects there. The first project was focused on targeted therapy for myelodysplastic syndrome (MDS). We focused on targeting a specific transcriptional factor pathway by using a drug that modulated a master regulatory of the pathway. The goal was to characterize the effects of the drug modulation in order to see if the target would be effective at treating certain MDS types. In this project, I learned flow cytometry, mouse handling/injections, western blot, incucyte, cell passaging, and drug treatment panels. For the second project, I focused on investigating the effects of certain pre-leukemic mutations in bone marrow transplant treatments for Sickle Cell Disease patients. We wanted to see if the presence of low frequency mutations in either the patient or donor would lead to complications post-transplant. In this project, I learned DNA extraction/library generation, gene sequencing/analysis, and DNA purification.

What is your favorite thing about research?

My favorite part of research is working together with the different people in the lab to overcome the problems that come up during research. Often in research, the outcomes are difficult to determine beforehand, which makes it important to enjoy the process and not the results.

What are your career goals and how do you hope to incorporate what you have learned from research in your future work?

My career goals are to get into medical school and pursue an M.D., most likely focusing in oncology. I hope that in the future I will be able to cooperate with more research focused people to help solve problems relevant to a patient treatment perspective. From research, I have learned to properly problem solve issues without a clear solution and also to understand that sometimes the results are not what was predicted but can still be highly useful.

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**Julia Florek
Carlson, 2024**

Major: Biochemistry

How did you become interested and involved in this field of study?

I knew that I wanted to work in a lab that

would allow me to explore my interests in biochemistry in the context of disease mechanisms. As I learned about the different research labs and opportunities within the Chem department, I gravitated towards many of the cancer-focused labs and was fortunate to land a position in the Stack Lab, which studies ovarian cancer. I have been a part of the Stack Lab ever since the start of my sophomore year, during which time I have been able to grow tremendously as a scientist and critical thinker.

What research have you conducted during your time in undergrad?

In addition to ovarian cancer research in the Stack Lab, I have also had the opportunity to conduct research in two labs abroad. During Summer 2022, I received the IRES fellowship to conduct organic synthesis research in the Hashmi Lab at the University of Heidelberg in Germany. I worked on a project concerning the functionalization of aromatic systems to optimize gold-catalyzed diyne cyclization reactions. While not an avenue of research I plan to pursue long-term, being exposed to organic synthesis was very valuable, as it helped me gain a more holistic understanding of the chemical underpinnings of drug design and inhibitors used in molecular biology research. During Fall 2023, I studied abroad in Galway, Ireland, and did research in the Glynn Lab, which studies human endogenous retroviruses (HERVs) in breast and prostate cancer. This experience served as the inspiration for my senior thesis, in which I am similarly examining HERVs but instead in the context of ovarian cancer, blend-

ing the foci of the Glynn Lab and the Stack Lab.

What is your favorite thing about research?

I really enjoy the collaborative aspects of research, whether it be presenting a poster at a conference, teaching/being taught by a fellow researcher, or bouncing ideas off of colleagues. I feel that often research is overly construed as a “solitary” activity - some aspects of it are, but teaching and presenting your findings to others is what allows research to truly make an impact!

What are your career goals and how do you hope to incorporate what you have learned from research in your future work?

I plan to take a gap year after graduation prior to pursuing an M.D.-Ph.D. I envision my future career consisting of both research and clinical work, as I aim to develop a perspective that synergizes and facilitates cross-talk between the two professions. I’m interested in continuing research related to oncology, or more broadly research with a focus on molecular mechanisms of disease.

Ian Schowe, 2024

Major: Biochemistry,
Political Science

How did you become interested and involved in this field of study?

I became involved in biochemistry because it was a chimera in science and I could connect a

lot. I could study chemistry while looking at different biological systems. It also has so many implications in drug design, medicine, cell biology, physiology, and structure. It is a cool field that can look at many topics with different angles and tools.

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What research have you conducted during your time in undergrad?

I have conducted research in Dr. Jessica Brown's biochemistry which looks at the triple stranded RNA, MALAT1 and its binding protein, METTL16. METTL16 is a methyltransferase that adds methyl groups to RNA (except not to MALAT1) which can affect if the RNA gets translated. I specifically studied METTL16 where I studied possible inhibitors, different possible DNA and DNA/RNA hybrid substrates, and I helped explore different METTL16 mutants, including cancer mutants with my graduate student. Most of my techniques have focused on running methylation assays for protein activity, mass spectrometry to see if the methylated nucleic acid base was present, and EMSAs or binding assays to obtain binding parameters between METTL16 (or its mutants) and possible substrates. The goal of this research is to understand more about this protein which can be dysregulated in different cancers. Moreover, since it has a role in gene expression, it is notable to look further into it.

What is your favorite thing about research?

I like collaborating with the other graduate students and undergraduate students. It is a great way to connect with the community as well as help get more input when you have to troubleshoot aspects of your project.

What are your career goals and how do you hope to incorporate what you have learned from research in your future work?

I am planning on becoming a physician scientist who practices medicine while conducting lab research. I hope to use my lessons from research to inform the type of fields I want to work on in the future. Moreover, the work ethic I have gained from my undergraduate research experience has toughened me up and prepared me for the best and worst that research has to offer.

**Lauren Beede,
2024**

Major: Psychology,
Statistics

How did you become interested and involved in this field of study?

I have always been interested in psychology, so majoring and studying it in college was a no-brainer to me. On the other hand, I took Calculus I in my fall semester of my first year and did not continue mathematics in the spring, and I found myself yearning for the quantitative challenge that psychology did not offer to the degree I desired. The following year I added ACMS as a supplemental major. That year, I wanted to conflate mathematics and the brain, so I reached out to Prof. Giuseppe Vinci, and we have been investigating statistical connectivity of the visual cortex since. During my sophomore year summer, I was also fortunate to have the opportunity to work in a small start-up company in San Jose, CA, called Deep Valley Labs. We investigated a spiking neural network for artificial intelligence development, and in my 10 weeks at the company, I gained valuable insight into theoretical/mathematical neuroscience and deep neural networks and enhanced my technical skills in Python and Linux. These experiences projected me into the field of computational neuroscience as I reached out to Prof. Robert Rosenbaum in my senior year to broaden my research in the discipline through state space models and now spiking neuron models in Python.

What research have you conducted during your time in undergrad?

First, I have been working with Prof. Giuseppe Vinci in the Department of ACMS for the past five semesters now. As a sophomore, Dr. Vinci eased me into research by assigning me to conduct various literature reviews to gain my footing in theory of spiking

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neurons as well as statistical methods well beyond a 2nd year's studies in undergraduate. We developed a research question around functional connectivity, or the statistical dependencies of neurons on each other. This was investigated using high-dimensional calcium imaging data from mouse V1 cortex in response to visual stimuli from a paper we selected. Secondly, I spent my summer of 2022 working at Deep Valley Labs (DVL) in San Jose, CA. This LLC investigated a variety of different ideas to be developed into start-up companies; my task was to research how the architecture of a spiking neural network affected its performance. My time at DVL was my first exposure to neural networks and Python. Diving into spiking neural networks without these core competencies proved a challenge, but I utilized my coworkers to frequently ask questions to gain footing in the theory. Thirdly, the following summer I participated in the Naughton Fellowship program in Dublin, Ireland. I was randomly assigned to a research group at the School of Computer Science and Statistics at Trinity College, Dublin, under Prof. Vinny Cahill. This group investigated optimizing simulated motorway traffic from an on-ramp using machine learning, deep reinforcement learning to be precise. Finally, I have also been working alongside Prof. Robert Rosenbaum in the Department of ACMS for the past two semesters, concurrently with Dr. Vinci. Under Dr. Rosenbaum, I have been reviewing literature about latent factor analysis of dynamical systems (LFADS), a tool which extracts the most important features of a temporal system in neuroscience.

What is your favorite thing about research?

I have found that I've learned the most from these research and summer experiences. Completing these hands-on tasks provides me with the opportunity to fail without feeling the consequences as an undergraduate researcher and ask questions because my mentors know I'm still fresh to research. To further build upon that, I am so grateful for the relationships I've been able to build with my professors at Notre Dame. I think ACMS research has been a

unique experience because Dr. Vinci and Dr. Rosenbaum are willing to meet with me directly and guide me through my questions and develop my thoughts more concretely. I've grown as a confident scholar in academia and researcher as a result of my mentors encouraging me to sit in on a visiting Ph.D. lecture or present my work at COS-JAM and COS-FURF and now beyond Notre Dame walls. The community is curious about what you research, and because of the supportiveness I have felt within academia at Notre Dame, I feel that people from a variety of disciplines provide insight and encouragement in avenues one would not think of in a unidisciplinary study.

What are your career goals and how do you hope to incorporate what you have learned from research in your future work?

I anticipate to continue research, not in academia but in industry, in computational neuroscience. This research has excited me for the past three years, and I still have much to learn about in the field because of its breadth. I'm a very flexible and "go with the flow" person, so I actually decided at the very last minute to pursue a Ph.D., resulting in delayed applications. I will be participating in a lab in academia to help project me towards my long term goals in industry research in neuroscience or artificial intelligence as the fields appear to be closing the gap between each other.

TALK SCIENCE

October 4, 2023

Beatriz de Campos Silva '24

“Exploring Plasma Radiation Effects on Solution pH for Medical Applications.”

Dr. Julian Torres-Dowdall

Department of Biological Sciences
Assistant Professor

“La Ecología Evolutiva de la Visión.”

November 9, 2023

Quinn Mackay '24

“Nonstationarity of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation’s fingerprint on Sea Surface Temperature.”

Dr. Brandon Ashfeld

Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry
Professor

“From Patient #9 to Avoiding Ozz-mosis: Transition Metal-Catalyzed Cycloadditions in Fluid Design and CNS Therapeutics Development.”

November 29, 2023

Becca Kubick '24

“Epigenetic Targeting Improves Glioblastoma and Breast Cancer Cell Sensitivity to Chemotherapy.”

Dr. Elizabeth Archie

Department of Biological Sciences
Professor

“Early Life Effects on Health and Behavior in Wild Baboons.”

January 24, 2024

Erik Finch-Soto '25

“Calbindin and Parvalbumin Expression in the Lateral Geniculate Nucleus Act as Potential Markers for Cell Class Identification.”

Dr. Diane Lane

Department of Biological Sciences
Assistant Teaching Professor

“Alpha-Synuclein Modulation of Dopamine Neurons is Critical for Drug Preference in Addiction.”

February 7, 2024

Carolina Jimenez '24

“Synthesis and characterization of a chiral cobalt organometallic complex and its reactivity with alkyl halides.”

Dr. Nick Edelen

Department of Mathematics
Assistant Professor

“Minimal surfaces and the mathematics of soap films.”

February 21, 2024

Corbin Hite '24

“The Effect of an Invasive Waterweed (*Elodea canadensis*) on Alaskan Freshwater Ecosystem Function and Pacific Salmon Populations.”

Dr. Quynh Lan Nguyen

Department of Physics and Astronomy
Associate Research Professor

“Dark Matter, Gravitational Waves, and the Origin of the Universe.”

The AMOC fingerprint, instead, shows dramatically different impacts of AMOC on SST in each regime.

Implies that NA SST could better reflect AMOC slowdown in rapid warming scenarios. AMOC likely plays a more minor role in SST change in more stable scenarios, introducing significant uncertainty.

Figure 5: Spatial maps indicating the AMOC fingerprint on SST

Reaction scheme showing the synthesis of a complex molecule. The reaction involves a starting material with a diazide group and a methyl ester, reacting with $\text{Rh}_2(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{PROL}_2$ in MeCN at -20°C to yield a product with a diazide group and a methyl ester. The yield is $>99\%$ and the enantiomeric excess (ee) is $>20:1$ d.r. Below the reaction are four vials containing liquids of different colors: yellow, green, dark green, and brown.

Diagram showing a horizontal bar with a scale from 0 to 1. The bar is divided into two sections: 'Shell' and 'Core'.

1 kHz to 4 kHz
- Step: 1 kHz

Glycine Concentration
0.01 M, 0.02 M,
0.1 M, 0.5 M

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